

**Enhancing Competitiveness, Resilience and Sustainability
of Remote Farming, Forestry and Rural Areas through
Holistic Assessment of Smart XG, Last-mile and Edge
Solutions' Gains**

D4.5: XGain Business models (1st version)

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
API	Application Programming interface
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AR	Augmented Reality
B2B	Business to Business
B2C	Business to Customer
BM	Business Model
BMC	Business Model Canvas
BMT	Business Model Tool
CBA	Cost Benefit Analysis
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
DSS	Decision Support System
EU	European Union
EO Sensors	Electro-Optical Sensors
GD	Goods-dominant
HaaS	Hardware as a Service
HDI	Human Development Index
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
ICT	Information and communications technology
IP	Internet Protocol
IT	Information Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
ISP	Internet Service Provider
KFT	Knowledge Facilitation Tool
LoRaWAN	Low-power, Wide Area Networking
M	Month
MCA	Multi Criteria Analysis
mHealth	mobile health
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
NGOs	Non-governmental Organisations
PaaS	Platform as a Service

PID	Public Improvement District
PPPs	Public-private partnerships
PuPs	Public partnerships
QoS	Quality of Service
R&D	Research and Development
SaaS	Software as a Service
SD	Service-dominant
SDBM/R	Service-Dominant Business Model Radar
SMEs	Small and midsize enterprises
UC	Use Case
V-AHP	Value Analytic Hierarchy Process
VLE	Virtual Learning Environment
VPC	Value Proposition Canvas
VR	Virtual Reality
Wi Fi	Wireless Fidelity
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The XGain project aims to promote sustainable and inclusive development in rural areas by providing access to a comprehensive inventory of smart XG, last-mile connectivity, and edge computing solutions for relevant stakeholders. The project's overall objective is to deliver a Knowledge Facilitation Tool (KFT) to aid in business model development and decision-making in selecting technology ecosystems that increase systemic resilience and energy efficiency, contribute to climate mitigation, and reduce digital divides among different groups.

This document is deliverable D4.5 “XGain Business Models”, the first report from Task 4.3 (Business Model Development and Assessment of Last-mile and Edge Technological Solutions), out of a total of two iterations to be carried out during the XGain project. The goal of this report is to provide innovative Business Models for three categories of actors i) End users (e.g., farmers and their associations, elderly houses, oyster farms, SMEs, etc.), ii) Public Authorities, and iii) Internet Service Providers (ISPs), based on their connectivity needs and ambitions for a number of sectors, services and actuators based upon 6 real life use cases. By taking into consideration the techno-economic feasibility as well as social and environmental impacts, XGain aims to develop new business models. The indicative Business Models will be incorporated into the Knowledge Facilitation Tool in order to be organised and give the possibility to key stakeholders to choose the most appropriate one.

Taking into consideration the complexity of digital connectivity as a whole (physical infrastructure, network providers, service providers), the presented herein Business models have been designed based on two fundamental assumptions stemming from XGain’s use case scenarios. A) XGain’s use case enablers will provide high-speed last-mile internet connectivity based on existing connectivity or “filling” existing networks’ connectivity gaps, and B) XGain’s Business Model Canvases will be designed based on “Last-Mile” Internet Service Provision (ISP) and its added value.

Given the plethora of Business Model tools that currently exist, a benchmarking was undertaken between a number of available tools and the Business Model Canvas tool was chosen as the most appropriate for serving the needs of XGain’s use cases. Through desk research, existing (state-of-play) and emerging business models for last-mile digital connectivity (per sector) was undertaken. After thorough research we came to the conclusion that there is a lack of related and specific information on digital connectivity business models directly linked to specific sectors. Desk research was also undertaken in an attempt to identify the market of the sectors of XGain’s interests and their potential based on the latest high-speed digital connectivity technological advancements and the usage of IoTs. To this end, our research revealed inadequacy of information regarding this highly specific concept (i.e., market development of high-speed digital connectivity and Aquaculture/Agriculture etc.). Instead, the increased market potential per sector is described, indicating (even indirectly) the necessity of last-mile digital connectivity towards competitiveness and sustainability of SMEs and other related stakeholders (located in rural areas with minimum if no digital connectivity) placed in the global market(s) environment.

Identification of an indicative value chain network (related to last-mile Internet connectivity) of stakeholders was undertaken and is presented in this report, together with their clustering and their interconnected relations and value streams, in an attempt to indicate a robust and efficient value chain network for last-mile Internet Connectivity. Lack of existing specific business models per sector based on last-mile internet connectivity paved the way for utilising the Business Model Canvas tool, specifically for XGain’s use cases, addressing/applied to specific sectors. As such, Business Model Canvases (KFT output) were created for each use case, addressing the three types of actors/users of the KFT based on their selections (i.e., sector, service etc.) and connectivity requirements.

Given the transformative potential of last-mile connectivity and edge technology solutions, coupled with the lack of information regarding last-mile internet connectivity addressing i) BM state-of-play for specific sectors, and ii) Market analysis for specific sectors, this report, amongst other, emphasises the need for a systematic and thorough methodology to evaluate their impacts. The meticulous approach adopted in this deliverable is integral to implementing these technologies in a manner that is not only sustainable and economically beneficial but also socially responsible across European rural areas' sectors and concomitantly to citizens.

1 Introduction

1.1 Mapping XGain Outputs

The increase in availability and usage of digital tools in all sectors (i.e., health, education, transportation, farming, etc.) demanded by the Covid-19 pandemic highlighted and amplified the already known digital connectivity inequalities existing between rural and urban areas. Digital accessibility and connectivity for rural communities and businesses still present a development challenge to many rural and remote areas. To this day, the lack of appropriate digital connectivity solutions for rural areas are directly linked, mainly, either to absence of the necessary technological infrastructure (non-sustainable for vendors), and/or due to high connectivity service prices making digital connectivity unaffordable for rural populations (non-sustainable for end users).

As the rural and coastal citizens are among the most vulnerable populations, every community's resilience, competitiveness, and capacity need to be enhanced, to contribute to and benefit from the upcoming transitions in a fair manner. Reducing the digital gap between rural and urban areas is of outermost importance; equally distributed digital opportunities translate to equal socio-economic opportunities for citizens and businesses. However, identifying a common solution for equipping rural communities with increased access to services, opportunities, and adequate innovation ecosystems is a challenging task, mainly due to the diversity of challenges and needs of different locations.

To encourage both private and public investments in fast and ultra-fast networks and enable individuals and businesses to fully benefit from digitalisation, the European Commission (EC) has implemented policy measures and financial instruments. The initial broadband provision objectives were:

- Basic broadband for all citizens by 2013. This target has been met, as satellite broadband is available in all Member States and has a 100% coverage;
- Coverage of Next Generation Networks (NGN): 30 Mbps or more for all citizens by 2020. Not met by all Member States by 2020;
- Use of NGN: 100 Mbps or more for 50% of households by 2020. Not met by all Member States by 2020.

Additionally, the EC has implemented regulations to decrease the expenses associated with deploying high-speed broadband. The cost of civil engineering works, which can vary depending on the terrain, can account for up to 80% of the total cost of deploying high-speed broadband networks. By minimising these costs, the roll-out of broadband can become more cost-effective.

Although all these measures have significantly improved the coverage of high-capacity networks, there are still variations between countries and rural areas. Remote and rural regions do have less access to high-speed broadband due to infrastructure challenges and the high cost of deployment. Rural communities are facing slower internet connections or relying on alternative technologies such as satellite or fixed wireless access, which may not offer the speeds required for advanced applications.

The XGain project in line with the ambitions of EU's Green Deal, the Digital Age and an Economy that works for people, ensuring that "No one left behind", aims to strengthen the capacities of farmers, foresters, and rural communities through digital connectivity gains. XGain fosters a sustainable, balanced, and inclusive approach for rural and coastal areas by facilitating access to relevant stakeholders, to a comprehensive inventory of smart XG, last-mile connectivity and edge computing solutions, and of related assessment methods.

Table 1 Adherence to XGain GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

XGain GA Component Title	XGain GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			

D4.5 XGain Business models (version 1)

Initial version including the overview of business models

TASKS			
Task 4.3 Business Model Development and Assessment of Last-mile and Edge Technological Solutions	Innovative Business models	Chapter 3.3	Provides an initial structure of BMs for end users, ISPs, and Public Authorities
	Business models state-of-play	Chapter 3	Presents an attempt to identify existing BMs on digital connectivity per sector through desk research
	Business models development	Chapter 2.1, 2.2	Explains the value of BMs in general
	Techno-economic and socio-environmental aspects	Chapter 4.2	Refers to these aspects as valuable supplementary work undertaken by other XGain Tasks and their incorporation in the KFT
	Market analysis for 7 different sectors	Chapter 3.1	Highlights the potential of sectoral markets that XGain’s use cases are applying last-mile internet connectivity

1.2 Document Scope

The present Deliverable 4.5 - XGain Business Models (1st version) is developed within the framework of Task 4.3 “Business Model Development and Assessment of last-mile and Edge Technological Solutions”; WP4 – XGain Knowledge Facilitation Tool Development. The aim of the deliverable is i) to present available business model tools, benchmark them and select the most appropriate fitting with XGain’s use case purposes, ii) to develop

preliminary innovative business models at systemic level for 7 different sectors, and iii) to develop the methodology of incorporating the business models to the KFT.

This document (D4.5) acts as a reference point to all XGain's use cases when carrying out testing and validation in real-life circumstances. Delivered in M13, D4.5 will be updated as D4.6 at M27, presenting progress with updates and improvements following the incorporation of feedback from the use case related stakeholders towards the finalisation of business models and final incorporation in the KFT tool.

1.3 Document Structure

The document is outlined in 7 chapters, structured to appropriately present the overall logic behind the creation of XGain's innovative business models for an efficient and effective integration and implementation in the KFT tool.

This document is comprised of the following 7 chapters:

Chapter 1 provides a summary of the project, the document scope, and its overall structure.

Chapter 2 provides an introduction on Business Models, various business model tools as well as their respective benchmarking.

Chapter 3 identifies the business models state of play for last-mile digital connectivity, proceeds with market analysis per sector, existing business models, financial tools and types of investment partnerships, the value network analysis and the innovative business models addressing XGain's use cases.

Chapter 4 indicates the KFT, its environment, the KFT input and outputs, the integrated techno-economic and socio-economic and environmental aspects, and the overall value-analytic hierarchy process methodology.

Chapter 5 explains the next step for the testing and validation of XGain's innovative business models.

Chapter 6 presents the conclusions of the deliverable.

Chapter 7 References

2 Introduction to Business Models

The Covid-19 pandemic has brought about new trends like teleworking and e-commerce, prompting the need for increased digitalization across various sectors, including health, education, transportation, and agriculture. However, these trends have also highlighted the existence of digital territorial inequalities, supply-chain disruptions, and economic deficiencies in rural communities, hindering their resilience and prosperity.

By developing innovative business models that address rural areas' specific needs and challenges, we can spark interest in environmental topics, promote local initiatives on climate neutrality, and empower people to take meaningful environmental actions. These initiatives will not only drive positive environmental impact but also foster economic growth and social development within rural communities.

XGain encourages exploration for alternative and innovative business models with a congruent design encapsulating value creation, delivery, and capture (shifting from product to service business models), aiming to facilitate the adoption of smart XG, last-mile and edge solutions by rural and remote areas.

2.1 Definition and Importance of business models

2.1.1 Introduction

Business models are usually generated by strategic management tools that can visualise and assess concrete business ideas or concepts. **A business model tool represents different fundamental elements of a business and aims to clarify how different aspects of the business are related to each other.** The goal of a business model tool is to provide a quick overview of the business model without many details (compared to the traditional business plan). The visual nature of the business model tool should make it easier to refer to and understand by anyone.

Given that it is the purpose of this report is to elaborate on the applicability of Business Models in the *use cases* that are being carried out within the purview of the implementation effort, working definitions of Business Models and Business Model Tools will provide the theoretical bedrock upon which the application of BMs is deemed appropriate in order to sufficiently explore, inter alia, the potential commercial opportunities and competitive advantages that the *use cases* represent.

2.1.2 Business Models

For the purposes of this deliverable further exploration, albeit brief, of both definitions, as stated below, is deemed essential in order to set up the conceptual framework upon which relevance between Business Models, and consequently Business Model Tools, and the **XGain** project can be established.

Consequently, as Business Model Tools are intended to determine the value of the transmitted information that a Business Model produces between the interested parties and to prioritise these transmissions by, e.g. peeling off the less essential in a more comprehensive, often visual in nature state, then it is appropriate that first a brief definition of Business Models is established and then of Business Model Tools.

Therefore, a Business Model can be defined as:

- An architecture for the product, **service** and **information flows**, including a description of the various business actors and their roles; and
- A description of the potential benefits for the various business actors;

- A description of the sources of revenues.

However, as literature stipulates, a Business Model “*in itself does not yet provide understanding of how it will contribute to realise the business mission*” of any of the *use cases*; Literature sources refer to companies, however the purpose of this report is to apply Business Models and Business Model Tools in the use cases of the project. However, Business Models are essential in exploring value chains, through value chain deconstruction and reconstruction (Timmers, 2006). In brief, as illustrated in Figure 1, value chain deconstruction refers to the identification of the distinguishable elements that comprise the value chain itself, while value chain reconstruction refers to the processing of information as it flows across the elements of the value chain, in this case stakeholder groups, project partners, market entities etc.

Figure 1 Value Chain Deconstruction

The pre-eminent example of value chain deconstruction can be found in Porter’s work, who also coined the term (Porter, 1985). His depiction maintains its relevance and suitability and his deconstruction of the value chain into nine (9) elements remains relevant in literature today but also serves as the go-to methodological approach for many applicable cases. Even though the value chains of the Project’s use cases are being elaborated upon in other instances and are being scrutinised thoroughly during the implementation process itself, it is essential that the theoretical framework behind the work is understood and elaborated upon sufficiently. However, the deconstruction of the key elements of each use case will be exemplified in the following chapters, during the development of each relevant Business Model.

Interaction Patterns that emerge from these processes are also examined and are essential when formulating the Business Models, given that they enumerate the number of parties involved in information exchange and thus manifest as a *mapping* of the information exchange flows within the model. It should be noted here that “[...] the a priori feasibility of technical implementation of the architecture of any business model depends very much upon the state-of-the-art of the (available) technology”; given that the project showcases the use of innovative and *new* technologies this proposition takes on additional significance, as the application of the appropriate Business Model is augmented, or diminished, if such is the case, by the application of the technologies introduced. This is true for the support of the interaction patterns as well. As such, the mapping of the interaction patterns represents a focal point of interest in this particular report, since it is a depiction not only of informational exchanges but also financial flows and, consequently, of economic opportunity. As one moves outwards from the core of the Business Models, interaction patterns emerge that indicate economic

opportunities other than the ones which are examined by each use case. For example, opportunities having to do with alternate revenue streams stemming from, e.g., economies of scale become visible. Such interaction patterns can be observed in the following chapters, where the Business Models of each use case are showcased.

In any case, the theoretical framework of Business Models is continuously evolving and, consequently, definitions abound, according to the scope and purpose of the Business Model. However, having set the theoretical foundations upon which BMs develop it is easier to address their suitability within the scope of implementation effort and appropriateness when trying to explore the economic opportunities that emerge from the **XGain's** use cases.

In conclusion, Business Models “*describe the core logic of how an enterprise creates and captures the value of innovations*” (Athanasopoulou and De Reuver, 2020). In the case of the **XGain**, the Business Models which will be developed below are meant to describe the innovation contained within the use cases and reconnoitre potential economic opportunities that arise from their implementation. A core aspect of the Business Model architecture are its interaction patterns, i.e., the way the different elements of the value chain exchange information and value, economic or otherwise and which also create the Business Model landscape. Understandably, different Business Models observe and scrutinise different interaction patterns and different elements of the value chain.

Given the above, it becomes apparent that two distinct issues are of particular importance: the first is to select the most appropriate and applicable Business Model when exploring the economic potential of the use cases. As indicated above, there is **great variety in Business Models** and each Business Model considers its value propositions in its own way, scrutinising different elements of the value chain and observing particular interaction patterns. This Business Model exploration is a common enough *thing* when trying to investigate the added value of an innovation, i.e. this iterative process through which business models are proposed, compared and subjected to experimentation until a revised and presumably successful business model is reached (Sosna et al. 2010). This issue will be addressed in the following chapter, where a review of the most suitable Business Models will take place and the most pertinent will be selected. The second is to decide whether the focus of the Business Model will be a product or a service, given that the **XGain** use cases are so varied one could briefly argue that in some use cases the line is blurred between the two. However, this is a faux pas, since even cursory study of the use cases indicates that they are consistent of both technological innovation and methodological innovation, leading to the definite conclusion that **the use cases should be considered as services and any potential value propositions should take this as a given**. Being services though, this means that a definition of the service-dominant market should be established, albeit brief and succinct, which will be addressed directly below.

2.1.3 Business Model Tools

“*Business model tools are commonly used to describe and communicate business model ideas*” (Athanasopoulou and De Reuver, 2020) and are conceptualised, in research, as boundary objects that are meant to make possible the exchange of information between, often disparate in nature, stakeholders (Bouwman et al., 2017). For the purpose of this report an apt definition of Business Models Tools can be found in (Bouwman et al. 2020), where Business Model Tools are described as “*the use of methods, frameworks or templates (here referred to as tools) to facilitate communication and collaboration regarding Business Model analysis, (re-)design, adoption, implementation and exploitation*”. This is of particular importance when addressing the theoretical framework

of the Business Model Tools, since it places them in the *broader literature of BMs*, a fact that emphasises the coherent nature of the link between the two.

It should be noted here upfront, however, that a significant division can be found within the Business Model Tool ranks: while some Business Model Tools cover the full scope of a Business Model, the best example being the *Business Model Canvas* which will be examined, inter alia, in the following chapter at length, others focus on particular aspects, e.g. the *Value Proposition Canvas* (Athanasopoulou and De Reuver, 2020). This sub-grouping is of particular interest to the purposes of this report since in following chapters, where Business Model exploration takes place concerning the **XGain's** use cases, the ability of a Business Model Tool to address the totality of a Business Model can be considered as a *decidingly important* argument for the selection of a particular Business Model and Business Model Tool.

Getting back to theory, as boundary objects, Business Model Tools must be both "*plastic enough to adapt to local needs and the constraints of the several parties employing them, yet robust enough to maintain a common identity across sites*", i.e., Business Models and, consequently, Business Model Tools must be able to incorporate and convey data for actors across the value chain, in most cases, however disparate these actors or the information itself may be. A popular such composition is proposed by Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010), comprising, again, of nine building blocks: value proposition, partner networks, customer segment, customer relationship, channel, key resources, activities, revenue streams, and cost structure. In any case, it becomes apparent that literature continuously addresses the necessary nature of Business Models to incorporate different data, compromise information from different - and often divergent - viewpoints but to always be *then* able to integrate this data into a single, coherent *message*³. This message can be best communicated through Business Model Tools and must be *robust* enough to maintain its form and integrity regardless of the receiver's capacity to comprehend. This is particularly so in the case of the Project where, by definition, there is a plethora of stakeholders engaged in the use cases, across the *quadruple helix*, i.e. having quite differentiated viewpoints and engagements with the Business Model. Moreover, these stakeholders not only have a different level of understanding concepts but they may also have differentiated interests, e.g. an Internet Service Provider (ISP) has the technical know-how to get to grips with the technical aspect of the use case and may draw on this knowledge in order to understand the *message* of the Business Model. At the same time a farmer may not share the same technical know-how, but he may focus on the benefits that are to be gained which are exemplified by the Business Model. In both cases these two **different stakeholders need to be able to understand the main message of the Business Model and make rational decisions based on the information**; as such, the message needs to be *plastic enough* to engage both stakeholders' interest but *robust enough* to maintain its integrity, in order to remain relevant to all. As such, it needs to compromise highly technical information from a number of sources, but then be able to transmit this information seemingly to all stakeholders, without loss. This is also the reason why choosing the appropriate Business Model Tool is essential, because the *interpretive flexibility*, i.e. the building blocks that comprise each Business Model, is of great importance when the grouping process takes place and the boundaries of the *object*, i.e. the Business Model Tool, are set: different Business Models have different building blocks, this arguably leads to different *architectures* (Star, 2010) and renders Business Models either more suitable or less suitable for specific uses cases.

To encapsulate, the particular worth of the Business Model Tools lies in the fact that they are *plastic enough* to accept disparate information from various sources. In the case of the **XGain** this is particularly evident since the

³ added value of an emergent opportunity

Business Models will have to handle information from a variety of different stakeholders: eg some producing science, others engaged in public administration, still others coming from industry and so on . At the same time BMTs *robust enough* to be able to communicate one message at the end, a message that can be understood by and benefit all parties. Since, as stated before, in the following chapter various Business Models and Business Model Tools will be explored in order to establish which will be the most appropriate to investigate the value proposition(s) of the use cases, all of these characteristics of the Business Model Tools, i.e., plasticity, robustness, coherence & the ability, or not, to address the whole scope of a Business Model, will be taken into consideration.

2.1.4 The Service-dominant logic

As a final preamble to the exploration of the various Business Models and Business Model Tools it is important to address briefly the *kind of market* which the **XGain's** use cases' Business Models and Business Model Tools are meant to describe. It is impossible, here, to distinguish between different markets since the use cases may deal with completely different market segments or markets altogether; this will take place during the following chapters where market analyses of the use cases will be performed. This is why only the *logic or mindset that is related with the offering of a service* will be examined here, regarding its theoretical framework and how it affects an economic actor's behaviour in any given market. As stated before, any potential business opportunity that arises from the **XGain's** use cases require the uptake of *a service*, this becomes evident by reviewing each use case. As such, and while a lengthy theoretical review of the service-dominant logic would elude the purpose of this report, a definition of the type of market that the Business Models and Business Model Tools will attempt to address is deemed relevant and a juxtaposition with the product-dominant logic (Figure 2) will help accentuate the characteristics that the Business Model and Business Model Tools, which will undertake the task of investigating potential values, will need to exhibit.

Goods Dominant Logic	Service-Dominant Logic
Goods	Service(s)
Tangible	Intangible
Operand Resources	Operant Resources
Asymmetric Information	Symmetric Information
Propaganda	Conversation
Value Added	Value Proposition
Transactional	Relational
Profit Maximization	Financial Feedback

Figure 2 Goods and Services dominant logic

The main focus of the service-dominant logic is that *markets*, and especially those that are dealing in services, are moving away from a logic that was *heavily based upon what is tangible* and are adopting a new mindset, the service-dominant mindset. This is not a *new realisation* and has been happening for some time now, nevertheless its temporal effect is still very much in effect to the present day. The service-dominant mindset *rejects the traditional distinction between goods and services and focuses on the relationship(s) between them* (Lusch et al., 2006). As such, this logic focuses on services offered rather than products produced, on intangible assets rather than tangibles, on symmetric information rather than asymmetric information and so on. A clear juxtaposition

of the two logics can be seen above, which helps make the difference between the two mindsets better felt and understood.

Albeit the theoretical framework presents its own appeal, how theory manifests within the **XGain's** use cases is, of course, more material. As such the core aspects of the service-dominant logic will be briefly enumerated below and the benefits that adopting such a logic (and, consequently, the appropriate Business Model) will become apparent.

- **Focus on services (rather than products):** This is self-evident since most use cases are best represented by a service-logic rather than product-logic.
- **Intangibles (rather than tangibles):** The shift from to intangibles focuses the BM on the solution, which is directly applicable to the use cases, as experimental solutions themselves to the problems posed by the topic.
- **Operant resources (rather than operand):** Most operant resources are intangible and dynamic, in service-dominant logic knowledge is the *“primal source of wealth and the only sustainable source of competitive advantage”*. Given that the **XGain** is producing new knowledge it is evident that the use cases can be viewed as operant resources, dynamic in nature due to the fact that they are now generating results.
- **Asymmetric to Symmetric (knowledge):** The **XGain** is a perfect example of how symmetric knowledge can produce an equitable outcome, since all partners participate in the implementation process and the use case, from which potential economic opportunity emerges, is the result of this symmetric collaborative process.
- **Value Added to Value Proposition:** In the goods-dominant logic, value is thought of as a property of a product - an attribute that is added during production. As such costs are accrued during production and *passed down through the value chain*. Value proposition, on the other hand, focuses on the desire of the customer to benefit from the results of the added value.

There are, as indicated in the table above, other distinct differences between a product-dominant market logic and a service-dominant market logic, however from the above it becomes apparent that the Business Models and Business Model Tools that will be employed to explore the **XGain's** use case should be imbued with a service-dominant logic. Recognizing the *type of logic that the market* should exhibit will facilitate the process of investigating where a viable opportunity lies and how a business proposition can be brought to market.

2.2 Types of business models

“A good business model answers Peter Drucker’s age old questions: Who is the customer? And what does the customer value? It also answers the fundamental questions every manager must ask: How do we make money in this business? What is the underlying economic logic that explains how we can deliver value to customers at an appropriate cost?” (Verrue, 2015)

Theoretical definitions of the Business Model and, consequently, the Business Model Tools were presented in the previous chapter and an effort was made to establish a direct link between the revelations of theory and the reality of Project implementation: as the **XGain's** use cases produce innovation it is now the work of this Report to review the most appropriate Business Model (and Business Model Tools) available in order to ascertain which one of these will be best suited to describe the value proposition of each use case.

This exploration of the Business Model landscape will establish which Business Model is best suited to tell the story of how the value proposition of each use case works and where opportunities lay - and how to deliver them to market.

2.3 Business Model development tools

2.3.1 Common Business Model Tools

Below, there are brief descriptions of commonly employed Business Model Tools that enjoy widespread usage:

- Business Model Canvas
- Business Model Canvas & Public Governance
- Lean Startup Canvas
- Value Proposition Canvas
- Business Model Radar
- Prototype Canvas

2.3.1.1 Business Model Canvas

“The Business Model Canvas is a strategic management and entrepreneurial tool. It allows you to describe, design, challenge, invent, and pivot your business model.” - Alex Osterwalder & Yves Pigneur, inventors of the Business Model Canvas.

The Business Model Canvas is a Business Model Tool, i.e., it is a visual chart with elements describing a company’s or product’s value proposition, customers, infrastructure including its partnerships, and financial aspects. It has been widely adopted in practice for designing business models (Osterwalder and Pigneur 2010). However, it follows an organisation-centric approach that renders the model from the perspective of a single company, as opposed to a network-centric view (Turber et al. 2015). It focuses on the processes controlled by the focal company and pays less attention to the customers’ active role in value co-creation.

A particular characteristic of the Business Model Canvas is that Osterwalder and Pigneur, who invented the Business Model Canvas, insisted that the Business Model Canvas should always be a one-page document (Figure 3). The main reason for this is that, the Business Model Canvas being a Business Model Tool should bear a single, robust message: how to implement the strategy of the Business Model. Another reason is that Osterwalder advised the use of graphical icons in business modelling as much as possible (Prabhu et al. 2013) in order for the message to be pithy and succinct:

Figure 3 Business Model Canvas

The Business Model Canvas, understandably, incorporates the nine (9) building blocks: value proposition, partner networks, customer segment, customer relationship, channel, key resources, activities, revenue streams, and cost structure (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010). A brief explanation of each block is presented below:

1. **Key activities:** The most important activities in executing a company's (or, in the case of the Project, a use case's) value proposition
2. **Key resources:** The resources that are necessary to create value for the customer. They are considered assets to a company (or, in the case of the Project, the Partnership) that are needed to sustain and support the business. These resources could be human, financial, physical and intellectual.
3. **Key networks:** In order to optimise operations and reduce risks of a business model, organisations usually cultivate buyer-supplier relationships so they can focus on their core activity. In the case of the Project such networks are expected to emerge from the networks of each participating partner, but also from networking activities undertaken by the implementation effort itself.
4. **Value propositions:** Services a business (or, in the case of the Project, an economic actor in general) offers to meet the needs of its customers. The value proposition provides value through various elements such as newness, performance, customization, "getting the job done", design, brand/status, price, cost reduction, risk reduction, accessibility, and convenience/usability. The Project's use case results should be at the core of the value proposition.
5. **Customer segments:** To build an effective business model, any economic actor offering a service must identify which customers it tries to serve. The Project's use cases will provide a point of direction for this particular building block, but it is also the main task of the Business Model to determine potential customer segments for its use cases.

6. **Channels:** The Project can deliver its value proposition to its targeted customers through different channels. Effective channels will distribute the value proposition in ways that are fast, efficient and cost-effective. In the case of the XGain, the value proposition can reach potential clients through channels developed during the project's lifetime (store front), partner channels (major distributors), or a combination of both.
7. **Customer relationships:** To ensure the survival and success of any business endeavour, responsible Project Partners will have to specify the type of relationship they want to create with their identified customer segments. In the case of the Project, that element should address two critical steps of a customer's relationship: How the new business will get customers and how the business will keep customers purchasing or using its services.
8. **Cost structure:** This describes the most important monetary consequences while operating under different business models. The cost structure can be cost-driven and value-driven. Given that costs are absorbed in the case of the Project through its funding, the cost structure is expected to be value-driven.
9. **Revenue streams:** The way the potential business opportunity is expected to generate income from each customer segment. This building block is expected to be further elaborated upon further in the analysis.

In conclusion, the Business Model Canvas is a Business Model Tool which has met with wide acceptance from the business community and beyond. Its plasticity has rendered it immensely popular amongst other Business Model Tools and its robustness has solidified its reputation as a valid tool for Business Model implementation.

2.3.1.2 The Business Model Canvas & Public Governance

Another, unique one could say, aspect of the Business Model Canvas is the fact that, due to its applicability, all-aroundness and its value-centric approach, the Business Model Canvas is either the only one (or one of a very select few) Business Model Tools that are being benchmarked in order to establish whether Business Model Canvas can also prove useful in providing a similar service to the description of *Governance Models*. Information on the subject appears to be exiguous since this is an endeavour that only recently has begun to be addressed sufficiently in research, however systematic knowledge has begun building up with auspicious results.

While the concept of *Public Governance* is a topic that merits its own exploration, it should be investigated elsewhere within the report. However, it should be noted, here, that it is a concept that *encompasses a new rhetoric that describes innovations in governing* (Kooiman, 1993). International literature on the issue abounds, but of particular interest is the fact that one can draw parallels from public-governance being made of multi-paradigmatic elements (Aguilar, 2006) to the particularities of the Union, i.e., EU's multi-level governance; in fact, it is almost inescapable here not to remember Blatter when he described: "[...] *we are witnessing a multiplication of layers of governance, a process which critical geographers have called "relativization of scales". Scholars of European Integration use terms like "multi-level governance" [...] Those who do not focus exclusively on the European Union have introduced the neologism "glocalization" to indicate the stronger interdependencies and interactions between local and global actors*" (Blatter, 2004). One could argue that multi-level governance is a particular European expression of the innovations of public governance, and that may well be true. But it is the complexity of the interactions (i.e. interference patterns) that these administrative innovations are introduced that are of interest here. And the reason why researchers have explored the possibility of using the Business Model Canvas to visualise aspects of the governance chain (Martins, 2011).

This all comes to fruition in the proposition of the Public Governance Canvas (Martins et al. 2017) (Figure 4). In their proposition of the *Public Governance Canvas* Martins et alia state that their goal was to "*expand (the*

Business Model) beyond its early origins in Information and communications technology (ICT) to become a management tool supporting organisations that create and deliver value to their beneficiaries through products (goods and services) in a sustainable manner”. And they note that, even though there is still a lot of ground to cover in the approach, “the innovation of a governance model is a starting point toward transforming the logic of proposing, delivering, and appropriating public value”.

Figure 4 The Public Governance Canvas

Whether this call to investigate further the applicability of the Business Model Canvas to Public Governance will be answered in droves or whether it will go unanswered remains to be seen, however even this early attempt to correlate what is essentially a business tool with the public domain is a unique advantage that Business Model Canvas has over other Business Model Tools and of a particular interest of this Report.

2.3.1.3 Lean Startup Canvas

The Lean Startup Canvas, or Lean Canvas as it is most usually encountered, is an adaptation of Osterwalder’s and Pigneur’s Business Model Canvas which self-identified entrepreneur Ash Maurya proposed in his 2012 book *Running Lean: Iterate from Plan A to a Plan That Works* (Maurya, 2012). The Lean Canvas promises an actionable and entrepreneur-focused business plan, as it focuses on problems, solutions, key metrics and competitive advantages (Abdoun and Ibrahim, 2018). As is the case with the Business Model Canvas the Lean Startup Canvas is a Business Model Tool, i.e. its purpose is meant to convey a robust message in a succinct way.

It shares multiple common characteristics with the Business Model Canvas but it also draws heavily from *lean management methodology*, the purpose of which is to identify and do away with all non-value-added activities which are a potential source of improvement in any kind of business process. The lean perspective is to reduce waste and costs, to improve quality and gain better use of resources in order to deliver higher value to customers (Cabrita et al., 2016). Maurya's intent was to come up with a Business Model Canvas which would be more actionable and more easily understood than the original Business Model Canvas but it should also be more applicable to start-ups.

As was the case with the Business Model Canvas the Lean Startup Canvas is also meant to be kept at a single page-length; the concept is, as before, that the message should be apt, concise and succinct. It aspires, however, to prove even more *plastic* than its counterpart, in the sense that its purpose is to be used by anyone, implying

that the Business Model Canvas is largely reserved for those who share understanding of economic and business terminology (Figure 5):

Figure 5 Lean Startup Canvas

Since the Lean Startup Canvas draws so much from the Business Model Canvas and has such a similar appearance, it is deemed more useful to briefly number the differences between the two Business Model Tools, rather than enumerate, as was previously done, it's - also - nine (9) building blocks.

1. **Intuitive:** Lean Startup Canvas uses layman terms in order to become more appealing to every stakeholder and not only those with a specific skill-set or know-how.
2. **Customer-Problem-Solution Focused:** Lean Canvas prioritises customer-problem-solution. This exemplifies why the Business Model Tool is particularly geared to facilitate start-ups.
3. **Simpler:** Lean Startup is meant to be used as a stand-alone Business Model Tool, not requiring a complimentary Value Proposition Canvas [see following chapter], as is the case sometimes with the Business Model Canvas.
4. **Practical/actionable:** The rationale behind the development of the Lean Canvas is that it is entrepreneur-focused, making it more practical than a business plan and more actionable than the Business Model Canvas.

Whether the Lean Canvas delivers on its promise as a more actionable and simpler alternative to the Business Model Canvas is a question, however the particular focus of the specific Business Model Tool on startups is something that creates advantages but also poses limitations in its applications.

2.3.1.4 Value Proposition Canvas

The Value Proposition Canvas (VPC) is a strategic tool (Kandee, 2020) that helps organisations and businesses to understand and design the value they provide to their customers. It was created by Alexander Osterwalder and Yves Pigneur as part of their Business Model Canvas framework (Osterwalder et al., 2014). Clark et al., 2012 stated that at the centre of the Business Model Canvas there is the Value Proposition, which represents the value offered to customers and can be seen in Figure 6.

The Value Proposition Canvas is more than just a graphical representation of customer wants. It focuses specifically on the value a product or service offers to its target customers and how it addresses their needs and pain points (How to Use Value Proposition Canvas: The Definitive Guide, 2020). The Value Proposition Canvas can be used when there is a need to improve an existing product or a service offering or when creating a completely new offering.

The Value Proposition Canvas provides on the one hand, the analysis of the customer side which helps you to define your target customer segments, which are the specific groups of people or organisations you are trying to serve. You can identify their characteristics, behaviours, preferences, and needs. Understanding your customer segments is crucial for tailoring your value proposition effectively. On the other hand, the value proposition contains ways to solve customer problems, relieve concerns and meet expectations. When two canvases align, it indicates that the product and/or service contains the desired values by customers and thus, it helps the organisation design products and services that their customers want (Osterwalder et al., 2014).

As mentioned above, the Value Proposition Canvas is formed around two building blocks ((Lindic & Da Silva, 2011): by capitalising the experience in the area of the *Customer Segment*, ie Customer Jobs, Gains and Pains you are able to create *Value Proposition* for Products and Services, Gain Creators and Pain Relievers (Pokorna et al., 2015). Organisations need to create one profile for each customer segment.

Figure 6 Value Proposition Canvas (Source: Image adopted by gofurther.digital based on Clark et al., 2012)

Customer (Segment) Profile

The Customer (Segment) Profile breaks the customer down into its jobs, pains, and gains and describes a specific customer segment in a more structured and detailed way.

- **Gains** – Describes the outcomes and benefits that align with customers' expectations and needs. These can range from required, expected or desired to unexpected ones that might pleasantly surprise them. They include functional utility, social gains, positive emotions, and cost savings.
- **Pains** – Describes any sources of frustration that customers experience in the process of getting the job done. Pains also encompass potential negative consequences or risks associated with performing a task inadequately or failing to complete it altogether.
- **Customer jobs** – Describes what customers are trying to achieve in their professional endeavours and personal lives. These customer jobs might be tasks they're striving to accomplish, challenges they're working to overcome, or needs they try to satisfy.

Value (Proposition) Map

The Value (Proposition) Map breaks your value proposition down into products and services, pain relievers, and gain creators and describes the features of a specific value proposition in your business model in a more structured and detailed way.

- **Gain creators** – how the product or service generates customer benefits and contributes additional value to the customer.
- **Pain relievers** – outlines how your product or service mitigates specific customer pains.
- **Products and services** – include all the products and services an organisation is planning to deliver. When building this part of a Value Proposition Canvas, one should consider if the product/service can help customers to accomplish any job-to-be-done, how relevant the product/service is, and if it is tangible or digital/virtual, etc⁴.

Overall, the Value Proposition Canvas serves as a practical and user-friendly tool that guides businesses in developing products and services that genuinely address customer needs and create value, leading to more successful and customer-centric outcomes. By tailoring value propositions to specific customer segments, businesses can differentiate themselves in the market and create a competitive advantage.

However, the Value Proposition Canvas does not substitute the Business Model Canvas, it rather complements it. Value Proposition Canvas aims to help an organisation understand its customers better, meaning that it is usually used at the beginning of a startup, when adding a new feature to a product or in case when an organisation wants to expand its business into a new market or customer segment.

2.3.1.5 Business Model Radar

Changes in market dynamics, customer preferences, technological advancements, and competitive pressures are some of the reasons that drive organisations to transition into a service-dominant (SD) business setting. This shift is driven by the recognition that value is co-created through interactions between organisations and customers. By focusing on services, organisations can better align with customer needs, adapt to changing market dynamics, and create sustainable competitive advantages in today's rapidly evolving business landscape (Turetken and Grefen, 2017).

⁴ <https://businessmodelanalyst.com/value-proposition-canvas/>

The conceptual tool that can be used as a guiding reference for business model design is the Service-Dominant Business Model Radar (SDBM/R) (Turetken et al., 2018). A Service-Dominant Business model differentiates from the traditional business model by taking a network structure based on the service-dominant (SD) logic rather than the value chain approach of the goods-dominant (GD) logic (Lüftenegger, 2014). SDBM/R has a network-centric design at its core, allowing the composition of service design in multi-party business networks. It defines how the actors in the business ecosystem participate in value co-creation and what the cost–benefits distribution is (Figure 7).

Figure 7 Service Dominant Business Model Radar (SDBM/R) Template (source: Grefen et al., 2016)

In a SDBM/R the following main elements can be distinguished (Turetken et al., 2019, Lüftenegger, 2014, Lüftenegger & Softic, 2019) as shown in the picture above:

- The **co- created value-in-use** is the goal of the business model and constitutes the heart of SDBM/R.
- The **actor value proposition** represents the part of the central value-in-use contributed by a single actor.
- The next layer, **co-production activity** defines the activities that each actor performs in the business in order to achieve the co-creation of value, in other words its actor value proposition.
- The third frame **actor cost/benefit** represents the costs and benefits that an actor incurs and gains respectively, by performing co-production activities.
- The fourth and last frame represents the **actors** and they can be distinguished between Customer (contributes to the production of the value- in-use), Focal Organization (often initiates the setup of the business model and participates actively in the solution), Core partner (contributes to the essentials of the solution), and Enriching partner (enhances solution’s added value-in-use).

Designing service-dominant business models using the SDBM/R technique involves an engaging and iterative procedure that requires the direct involvement of the main stakeholders within the business model. Even though SDBM/R models are known for their user-friendly nature, they serve as a robust foundation for translating business models into conceptual business process models. These process models depict the real-world business

operations within collaborative networks, facilitating the effective implementation of the intended business strategies (Suratno et al., 2018).

2.3.1.6 Prototype Canvas

Prototyping is the process of creating a preliminary or initial version of a product, system, or concept to test and evaluate its functionality, design, and feasibility before proceeding with full-scale development. Prototyping is widely used in various fields, including software development, product design, and business strategy, to validate ideas, gather feedback, and identify potential issues early in the development cycle (Hansen et al., 2020). Developing prototypes is crucial to make value propositions tangible and concrete. However, the process of constructing a prototype is marked by substantial initial investments and a multitude of uncertainties. (Lauff et al., 2019).

Prototypes can take many forms (Heaslip, 2021) and in many cases the Business Model Canvas - since it is the most recognizable and successful business design tool in use (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010) - is influencing the structure of a Prototyping Canvas (Lauff et al., 2019). Prototype Canvas tool is recommended to consider after having filled in the Business Model Canvas and/or the Value Proposition Canvas.

Prototyping can be used in many phases of the product design, with different purposes. It can be used to find out if something is technically feasible (an 'engineering' prototype), if your design ideas look good, and satisfies design criteria, or if your ideas resonate with customers (a 'validation' prototype). Figure 8 below shows the validation prototype canvas.

Figure 8 Prototype Canvas (source: <https://www.designabetterbusiness.tools/tools/prototype-canvas/>)

Elements Overview⁵:

- **Customer's job-to-be-done** - Describe who is your customer and what is the job to be done for this customer.
- **Customer benefit(s)** - Describe what the customer gets out of it and when.
- **Customer Promise** - Describe what part of the customer promise you want to prototype and what is your promise to your customer.
- **Key Features** - Describe the key features and functionalities, focusing on the minimum required features.
- **Steps** - Describe the minimal steps the customer needs to go through to reach the job to be done and the benefits, if there are any alternatives and what is the experience per step for the customer.

Prototyping Canvas effectively guides designers through prototyping processes, facilitates a common prototyping language amongst team members. It encourages intentional prototyping practice, which should ultimately reduce resources and improve design outcomes.

⁵ <https://www.designabetterbusiness.tools/tools/prototype-canvas/>

2.4 Benchmarking and selection of tool

In this chapter, we explained what a business model is, why it is important, which types of business models' tools exist and what are the ways to compose a good and sustainable business model. The significance of the business model is perceived due to the fact that it is a tool that helps the organisation to:

- define where the business is in the value chain;
- determine what the consumer gets out of it;
- determine the future of a business – whether it succeeds or fails;
- achieve success of any business;
- create a foundation for optimising innovative technology;
- create a clear statement of the business mission and vision;
- create a set of values that can help to steer business;
- create a clear-eyed analysis of the industry, including opportunities and threats;
- create a portrait of potential customers;
- create a roadmap and timetable for achieving goals and objectives;
- create a résumé that can be used to introduce the business to suppliers, vendors, or lenders.

Numerous researches in the area of entrepreneurship have shown that a company simply cannot be successful without a good and firmly set business model.

A business model tool provides a quick overview of the business model including all crucial elements of a business and existing relations between them. While looking for the best suited business model tool for the **XGain's** use cases we analysed business model tools that are widely used and that can be applied in the context of the XGain project:

- Business Model Canvas,
- Lean Startup Canvas,
- Value Proposition Canvas,
- Business Model Radar and
- Prototyping Canvas.
- Public Governance Model

Many companies worldwide use **Business Model Canvas** as a compact and clear guideline for their businesses, but when it comes to entrepreneurships **Lean Startup Canvas** is a more suited option because it includes startup factors such as uncertainty and risk. Another business model tool that is especially recommended to startups is **Value Proposition Canvas**. It helps businesses to create a perfect fit between their products and market. The **Business Model Radar** places a strong emphasis on providing services as the core value proposition and revenue generator for the organisation and it is the proposed framework for business modelling of Data Spaces. This

approach contrasts with traditional product-centred models where tangible goods are the primary focus. When an organisation is still in the phase of product development, **Prototyping Canvas** can help with testing a certain aspect of the developing product or service. It effectively guides designers through prototyping processes and facilitates a common prototyping language amongst team members.

In the context of **XGain and the digital connectivity in remote areas**, we opted for the **Business Model Canvas** to gain a deeper understanding of the business models. This tool offers a more extensive approach compared to others and enables a greater level of complexity and detail to be incorporated. Its approach promotes a collaborative team dynamic by involving all stakeholders and encouraging active participation in the development, enhancement, and fine-tuning of the business model. This framework is versatile and can be customised to suit diverse business types, industries, and customer segments.

The following list includes a number of reasons why the Business Model Canvas is a suitable option for the XGain:

- **Simplicity and Clarity:** XGain use cases are placed in remote areas involving various stakeholders and complex ecosystems. The simplicity and visual clarity of the Business Model Canvas can help clearly define and communicate the different components of a digital connectivity initiative.
- **Comprehensive View:** The canvas covers various aspects of a business model, including key partners, customer segments, value propositions, and revenue streams. When working on digital connectivity in remote areas, we need to consider multiple elements, such as infrastructure, technology, partnerships, and customer needs. The canvas helps ensure we address all relevant aspects.
- **Value Proposition:** One of the critical elements of the Business Model Canvas is the value proposition. Understanding the unique value of digital connectivity, through the use cases, provided to communities or businesses in these remote locations is crucial. The canvas helps to define and refine the value proposition.
- **Partnerships and Resources:** In the context of remote connectivity, partnerships with local authorities, technology providers, and community organisations may be essential. The canvas allows you to identify and visualise these key partnerships and the resources required for each use case.
- **Cost Structure:** Operating in remote areas can come with unique cost challenges. The canvas enables us to outline and manage the cost structure effectively, helping us identify areas where cost optimization is necessary.
- **Customer Segments:** Understanding the specific needs and preferences of people or businesses in remote areas is vital. The Business Model Canvas encourages to define the customer segments, which can lead to more targeted and effective solutions.
- **Quick Iteration:** The canvas facilitates rapid iteration and experimentation, allowing us to make adjustments to our business model as needed.

3 Business Model State-of-Play

In the preceding chapter, we introduced the concept of Business Models and assessed various Business Model Tools. After a thorough benchmarking process, we decided that the **Business Model Canvas** is the most suitable tool to depict the business model of each XGain's use case. Next steps include an **overview of key existing business models for last-mile digital connectivity in remote areas** and the **development of new inclusive, innovative and sustainable business models** which will be **tested during the 6 use cases**.

Before we proceed with developing the Business Model Canvases per use case and per actor (see Section 3.4), it is crucial to collect and analyse information regarding the market landscape and its inherent potential. The first step is to conduct a **market analysis** and a thorough assessment of a market within a specific industry. It's important to carefully analyse starting conditions and adapt the business models accordingly. For instance, entering a saturated market versus a niche one, requires different approaches. Flexibility and the ability to pivot when necessary are also essential, as external factors may change over time, requiring adjustments to the business model. Market analysis is the foundation upon which a business model is built and they are closely correlated enabling businesses to create a business model that aligns with market realities and customer needs (Importance of Market Analysis in Improving Business Growth - Infiniti Research, 2018).

In the present deliverable we will identify and benchmark existing business models for **last-mile digital connectivity** in terms of

- actors
- starting conditions and obstacles faced
- enabling factors (including location-specific requirements, technologies and connectivity)
- associated costs and financing mechanisms
- generation of added value (ideally per actor)
- jobs and other potential environmental and social benefits
- gender issues
- attractiveness to young workers
- distribution of the value generated, exploring the concept of shared value

through desk research for each **different sector**,

- aquaculture
- agriculture
- forestry
- environmental monitoring
- e-health
- e-government
- tourism

and compare them with the business models of the XGain's unique use cases.

Building upon the assessments and benchmarks, alternative innovative business models will be developed, tested and validated in real life conditions during **M16-M35 in WP5** (across 7 sectors and in 6 different regions)

aiming to create added value, environmental sustainability, social cohesion and jobs, and are likely to be upscaled to or replicated in other areas.

The market analysis was also conducted for **last-mile digital connectivity in our seven sectors** mentioned above but after performing a thorough and comprehensive desk research endeavour, it has become apparent that there is a notable **absence of existing market analysis for last-mile digital connectivity across our seven sectors**. The lack of available market analysis is because:

- we target a **niche market** (although, this is often a characteristic of emerging or specialised market) because the XGain's use cases:
 - have been designed and will be implemented as “enhancers” or “data rate multipliers” or
 - as an addition of existing mobile networks in rural areas,
 - focused on last-mile internet service provision
- remote areas are dominant by small, local producers that have **not been extensively studied**

As a substitute for the absence of market data on digital connectivity across our sectors, we present market analysis per sector but instead of focusing on digital connectivity we pivot to market research and data from **related industries and analogous markets** that share characteristics with the XGain's services and sectors within the use cases.

The absence of market data pertaining to digital connectivity in remote areas significantly reduces the probability of discovering relevant existing Business Models tailored to this specific context. The absence of specific business models for remote areas in the context of XGain's use cases is rational taking into account the heterogeneous and unique services they provide per sector (see the following chapter).

As our primary desk research did not have any fruitful results, we have decided to modify our approach. This adjustment involves a shift in our research area to overcome the limitations and challenges we encountered during the initial phase of our research.

Our subsequent objective was to identify and analyse the existing business models employed by **Internet Service Providers (ISPs)** when it comes to serving remote areas. This goal involves a comprehensive exploration of how ISPs structure their services, pricing, and strategies specifically to cater to the unique challenges and opportunities presented by remote or underserved regions.

Our research findings indicate that **Internet Service Providers (ISPs) typically do not adhere to a standardised Business Model for providing digital connectivity in remote areas.** This approach is justified due to the multitude of distinctive features and constraints found in these areas, including factors such as population density, climate conditions, and terrain types. Instead, ISPs typically employ a single overarching business model that they adjust and customise according to the specific requirements of each situation. This approach reflects the industry's recognition that flexibility and adaptability are essential when providing digital connectivity, especially in diverse and challenging contexts like remote areas. The common characteristics that the business model employed by a number of indicative ISPs, have been identified and detailed in section 3.2.4.2.

Within the framework of the XGain project and its use cases, we have undertaken a comprehensive analysis to explore the avenues through which digital connectivity can be extended to remote areas. This analysis represents a focused examination of the strategies and methods for delivering reliable internet access to geographically

isolated or underserved regions. Section 3.4 presents XGain's initial Business Models, using the Business Model Canvas with the aim to **fine tune them accordingly in real-time and real circumstances during the implementation and execution of the use cases (M16-M35)**.

3.1 Market Analysis per sector

Before delving into the market analysis of each use case sector, you could find below a table containing concise descriptions of each use case, including their respective sectors and services offered (Table 2). These descriptions provide a deeper understanding of the specific sectors and services associated with each use case, highlighting the project's diverse range of applications aimed at addressing digital connectivity challenges in remote areas.

Table 2 XGain's Use case description, service and sector

Use Case # - Country	Service (s)	Sector(s)	Use Case Short Description
UC.1 - Spain	a) Drones operation in rural areas, b) Additional services with high data rate	Agriculture, Environmental Monitoring, Education, Tourism	The testbed in Mora la Nova aims to bring 5G technologies to rural areas and encourage their use by local educational institutions, the agricultural sector and SMEs through the dedicated network and computer resources segments. A series of drones will be deployed at the pilot site and connected via 5G to the operations centre, where various services such as monitoring, and video/image processing will be carried out. The pilot site also aims to work on an economically and environmentally sustainable model for rural 5G-based networks and explore potential business models for local agriculture and SMEs looking to expand their services using drones.
UC. 2 - Greece	a) A E-Health robot that will act as a virtual caregiver for the elderly, b) High data rate services c) Tourism	e-Health, e-Governance, Education, Tourism	The E-Health Robot aims to serve as a virtual caregiver for the elderly, providing monitoring and advice. The service offers interventions aimed at improving well-being, including cognitive exercises, nutritional guidance, physical exercises, and social recommendations (online workshops). These interventions are projected through a mini-projector and assisted through a speakerphone, which can receive user commands and provide spoken feedback. The projected interventions include daily insights, memory-enhancing quizzes and games, nutritional advice, and recommendations to promote socialisation.
UC.3 - UK	a) Precision Agriculture b) Tourism	Agriculture, Tourism, Env. Monitoring	This use case addresses the problem of limited network coverage on the remote Isle of Scilly (UK). 5G technology and balloons/drones will be deployed to improve network coverage and demonstrate the digitisation and precision farming techniques 'n an island's small-scale vegetable farm (Scilly Organics). The goal is to extend the tested and validated solutions to the entire island, ensuring 100% coverage and providing local and currently disconnected communities with access to services for agriculture, land maintenance, recycling and other areas. The cost of equipment for the demonstration will be covered by the project, but an operational business model with funding from the local municipality or mobile network operators will be established. The project also explores cross-sector business models between agricultural activities and tourism needs.

<p>UC.4 - Lithuania</p>	<p>a) Precision Agriculture b) Forest Management</p>	<p>Agriculture, Forestry</p>	<p>This use case explores deploying a 5G network in an arable farm in Lithuania to improve crop health and nutrient composition assessment using innovative crop assessment technology based on drones/planes and hyperspectral cameras. This use case aims to provide hybrid solutions of local and edge- or cloud-based solutions to efficiently handle data transfer from areas with limited internet connectivity, such as agricultural fields or forests. The use case added value is to enable near-in-situ analysis and near-real-time decision-making, reducing the use of chemicals and fertilisers in agriculture and improving the efficiency and rapid evaluation of some forest monitoring data. The demonstration scenario is based on the power of the 5G technology, where collected data can be sent directly from the drone to the server (cloud), after being preprocessed with onboard technologies.</p>
<p>UC.5 - Croatia</p>	<p>a) Water quality monitoring b) Remote oyster farming</p>	<p>Aquaculture, Env. Monitoring</p>	<p>The Dalmatian region in Croatia, characterised by remote coastal and open sea areas, suffers from underdeveloped ICT infrastructure. This lack of connectivity is particularly challenging for the under digitised oyster farming industry, which needs to innovate in the face of climate change.</p> <p>Currently, inefficient, costly, and time-consuming manual data collection is the norm, especially in rural areas where connectivity is limited. XGain offers a solution, providing networking and data collection services that can optimise human resources, reduce costs, and enhance management efficiency.</p> <p>Moreover, XGain's real-time updates and forecasting services promise to create a more sustainable business environment. They offer potential benefits including increased operational efficiency, improved production quality, cost reduction for farms, and enhanced quality and lower prices for consumers. Importantly, the XGain solution can scale from nearshore areas to regions with even more limited data transmission availability.</p>
<p>UC.6 - Belgium</p>	<p>a) Livestock health b) Farm management</p>	<p>Agriculture</p>	<p>The "digital shepherd" aims to address the digital divide between extensive and intensive livestock farming in Flanders, Belgium. The solution involves using a camera system and drones to monitor herds in small pastures and remote areas. The goal is to develop a service that can be adapted to different farming ecosystems and provide real-time monitoring services that ensure animals are constantly observed, relevant events are captured for the farmer, and targeted alerts are generated. The solution aims to improve productivity and welfare and reduce stress for the farmer. The demonstration will show the application on farms with solid network connectivity and poor network conditions. The cameras and drones will be equipped with</p>

			connectivity to generate alerts and analytics tailored to the specific application, in areas with strong and poor network coverage.
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3.1.1 Aquaculture

3.1.1.1 Use Case(s), services and related sectors

The **Use case No 5 in Croatia** belongs to the Aquaculture sector. The services the use case provides are **(i) Water quality monitoring and (ii) Remote oyster farming**. Despite the fact we were unable to find any existing market analysis on **digital connectivity in the Aquaculture sector**, the XGain project recognises the importance of developed ICT infrastructure and how challenging the lack of connectivity can be. The under digitised oyster farming industry needs to innovate in the face of climate change through the utilisation with the latest digital technological advances stemming from all sorts of IoTs (e.g. water temperature sensors, etc.). XGain offers a solution, providing networking and data collection services, that can optimise human resources, reduce costs, enhance management efficiency and create a more sustainable business environment. Additional potential benefits include increased operational efficiency, improved production quality, cost reduction for farms, and enhanced quality and lower prices for consumers.

Following, we present a similar market analysis as a substitute. While this is not a perfect match, this approach can provide valuable insights to understand the market and its growth potential.

Our research focused on **Global Aquaculture Market, Global Oyster Farming Market and Water Quality Monitoring Systems Market** sizes, their growth and trends and the key players of each market with the aim to understand the dynamics, opportunities and challenges within the Aquaculture industry.

3.1.1.2 Market Definition and Scope

Aquaculture, often referred to as aquafarming, is the practice of cultivating aquatic organisms (El-Sayed, 2020) (such as fish, crustaceans, mollusks, aquatic plants, and algae) under controlled conditions. It involves the breeding, rearing, and harvesting of these organisms in various water environments, including freshwater, brackish water, and marine environments. Aquaculture is an important sector of the global food production system and plays a significant role in meeting the increasing demand for seafood (Ahmad et al., 2021). The aquaculture sector's rapid advancement is attributed to innovations in production systems, and it has consistently represented 8.8% of the annual total food industry since 1980. Despite being a relatively young industry, there remain numerous unexplored areas for the continued development and expansion of aquaculture (Ahmad et al., 2021).

3.1.1.3 Market Size and Growth

The Global Aquaculture Market is expected to grow at a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 5.5% from 2022 to 2030 reaching a market size of \$ 421.2 billion (Vantage Market Research, 2023) (Figure 9). The Aquaculture market on a global scale is projected to experience substantial growth in the forecast period. This expansion is attributed to shifts in the lifestyles of the working population, accompanied by advancements in technology within equipment and production techniques. Research indicates that individuals now allocate less time to cooking at home, resulting in an increase in the consumption of meals from external food and beverage sources. The growing trend of high-protein diets, coupled with an uptick in eating out, will contribute to the broader reach of the global market (Vantage Market Research, 2023). The global population will increase to 8.5 billion in 2030, and to maintain the consumption per capita, which is estimated to reach 21.5 kg in the same year, the aquaculture industry needs to expand its production capability to an estimated 109 million tons (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2020).

Figure 9 Aquaculture Market size, 2022 to 2030 (USD Billion)

(source: <https://www.vantagemarketresearch.com/industry-report/aquaculture-market-2032>)

Digital technologies are of the utmost importance for the future of aquaculture. Digital transformation can positively influence the expanding needs of aquaculture industries resulting in novel breakthroughs. By bringing significant operational benefits for the global food chain, improving efficiencies and productivity, mitigating significant risks that can jeopardise seafood production and supply chain, new players will enter the space and the market will get more competitive (Rowan, 2023), (Market Reports World, 2023). By harnessing the power of digital connectivity, the aquaculture industry can address challenges, optimise processes, and contribute to sustainable seafood production that meets the demands of a growing global population (Bates et al., 2021).

As consumer expectations continue to change, companies at the forefront will introduce new products with innovative features or competitive pricing. Established industry leaders will strive to maintain their dominant positions, while emerging entrants will seek to establish their presence in the market.

The Aquaculture market is set to experience a gradual global growth trajectory, influenced by evolving consumption habits and the expanding retail sector. Moreover, the convenient accessibility of products through diverse distribution channels adds to consumers' ease in acquiring packaged Aquaculture items. The embrace of industry standards aimed at delivering disease-free fish, cultivated in environments adhering to required hygiene norms, is projected to bolster sales. The expanding agricultural sphere, coupled with the uptake of organic food offerings, is anticipated to significantly contribute to the increasing presence of the global Aquaculture market.

The Global Oyster Farming Market size is expected to expand at a CAGR of 5.5% from 2021 to 2030 reaching a market size of \$ 1.7 billion (Market Reports World, 2023) (Figure 10). Technological trends, fueled by heightened investment in research and development and a heightened emphasis on innovation among industry participants, are poised to exert a favourable impact on the Oyster Farming market. Anticipated substantial opportunities in the forecast period will attract newcomers to the field, intensifying market competition. According to the report, the evolution of consumer expectations will prompt the introduction of new products, boasting novel features or competitive pricing, as established market leaders prioritise preserving their forefront position while emerging entrants endeavour to establish their market influence.

Figure 10 Aquaculture market by species

(source: <https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/aquaculture-market>)

Driven by heightened demand from significant application sectors, the Oyster Farming Market is anticipated to sustain its growth trajectory. Macroeconomic influencers, including global economic expansion, swift urbanization, the burgeoning middle-class population, and enhanced consumer spending capabilities, are poised to propel growth within pivotal industries (Market Reports World, 2023).

- The global economic output was over USD 100 trillion in 2022. The top 5 economies (USA, China, Japan, Germany and UK) accounted for around 58% of the global economic output in 2022.
- By 2030, the middle-class population is expected to increase to over 5.5 billion, accounting for over 65% of the global population.
- The global GDP per capita is projected to reach USD 13,920 in 2025, a 35% increase in the 2015-2025 period.

To cater to the increasing consumer demand for products and services, industries are either broadening their product offerings or enhancing their production capacities. The emergence of diverse end-use sectors is anticipated to deliver a substantial upsurge to the market in the times ahead.

Oyster farms require specific water quality conditions to ensure the health, growth, and overall well-being of oyster populations. These conditions play a vital role in determining the oysters' growth rates, shell development, disease resistance, and overall quality (Parker & Bricker, 2020). A water quality monitoring system is utilised to gather and analyse data related to various parameters of a water body, encompassing its constituents and overall condition. These monitoring systems are employed for sampling and evaluating water quality across diverse sectors, including pharmaceuticals, life sciences, and the food & beverage industry. Within a water quality monitoring system, components like temperature sensors, dissolved oxygen sensors, turbidity sensors, pH sensors, among others, work collectively to facilitate the monitoring of a spectrum of water quality indicators. The degradation of water quality and the adverse health repercussions of water pollution have prompted numerous companies to innovate water quality monitoring devices (Allied Market Research, 2018). **The Water Quality Monitoring Systems Market size is expected to expand at a CAGR of 8.3% from 2018 to 2028 reaching**

a market size of \$ 7.5 billion (D’Souza & Singh, 2022) (Figure 11). Key drivers for the global water quality monitoring systems market's growth comprise the escalation of water pollution resulting from industrialization, the upsurge in waterborne diseases, and the heightened responsibilities undertaken by governments (Allied Market Research, 2018).

Figure 11 Water quality monitoring systems market size, 2018-2028

(Source: <https://www.kbvresearch.com/water-quality-monitoring-systems-market/>)

Development of policies and initiatives in order to reduce environmental pollution levels, advancements in technology to enable better water monitoring, rise in government funding for pollution monitoring and control, and increasing global levels of water pollution are majorly driving the market growth (Triton Market Research, 2023; Verified Market Research, n.d.) Amidst the significant applications within the water quality monitoring market, the laboratory application is projected to dominate the market share throughout the forecast period. Anticipated to exhibit the highest compound annual growth rate (CAGR) in the forecast period, this application is driven by the surge in water pollution and contamination due to swift industrialization and population expansion (Markets and Markets, 2017).

3.1.1.4 Competitive Landscape

- Global Aquaculture:** The worldwide Aquaculture sector features leading players expanding their array of products to address a broad consumer base. Furthermore, these players allocate resources to research and development units to enhance production output (Vantage Market Research, 2023). Additionally, the industry is marked by continual mergers, acquisitions, and the expansion of collaborative initiatives to uphold a competitive edge. The key players in the global Aquaculture market include among others - Alpha Group Ltd. (Canada), Aquaculture Technologies Asia Limited (Hong Kong), Cermaq Group AS (Mitsubishi Corporation) (Norway), Cooke Aquaculture (Canada), Leroy Seafood Group ASA (LEROY) (Norway), Marine Harvest ASA (Marine) (Norway), Nippon Suisan Kaisha Ltd. (Japan), P/F Bakkafrost (Faroe Islands), ASSAL Group Limited (Australia), Thai Union Group PLC (UNION Thailand) (Vantage Market Research, 2023).

- **Global Oyster Farming:** Some of the key players in oyster farming are Chatham Shellfish Company, France Naissain, Hog Island Oyster Company, Hoopers Island Oyster Company, Huitres Favier Earl, Huitres Helie, Mere Point Oyster Company, Morro Bay Oyster Company, Murder Point Oysters Company, Pangea Shellfish & Seafood Company Inc., Tomales Bay Oyster Company LLC, Westcott Bay Shellfish Company and White Stone Oyster Company (Imarc, n.d.).
- **Global Water Quality Monitoring Systems:** Some of the major players such as Danaher Corporation, Evoqua Water Technologies, General Electric Company, Horiba, Ltd., OAKTON Instruments, Pentair, Shimadzu Corporation, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Inc., Uponor, Xylem Inc. (Allied Market, 2018).

The market analysis of the Aquaculture industry reveals a dynamic and growing sector with significant global impact. With the increasing demand for seafood products and the challenges faced by traditional fisheries, aquaculture has emerged as a sustainable and vital source of food and feed products. The market size continues to expand steadily, driven by factors such as population growth, rising consumer awareness of the health benefits of seafood, and the depletion of wild fish stocks. The competitive landscape is characterised by a mix of established players and emerging market entrants, with a growing emphasis on quality, traceability, and product differentiation. With a burgeoning demand for aquaculture products, coupled with technological advancements and responsible practices, the aquaculture industry is poised for continued growth and innovation in the coming years.

3.1.2 Agriculture

3.1.2.1 Use Case(s), services and related sectors

Agriculture sector will be explored through the activities of **Use Cases No 1, No 3 and No 4** which are placed in **Spain, UK and Lithuania** respectively. The services those use cases provide are: **(i) Drones operation in rural areas** and **(ii) additional services with high data rate** in Use Case 1 - Spain, **(iii) Precision Agriculture** and **(iv) Tourism** in Use Case 3 - UK and **(v) Precision Agriculture** and **(vi) Forest Management** in Use Case - 4 in Lithuania. Although we were unable to find any existing market analysis on digital connectivity in the Agriculture sector, the XGain project acknowledges the significance of 5G technologies and networks in the agriculture sector and how it increases the competitiveness and social and environmental sustainability of the sector. XGain offers solutions (eg EO sensors, cameras, edge devices etc) that can optimise in-situ operations in the agricultural sector, reduce costs of agricultural practices and uptake precision agriculture techniques.

Following, we present a similar market analysis as a substitute. While this is not a perfect match, this approach can provide valuable insights to understand the market and its growth potential.

Our research focused on Global Agriculture Market, Global Digital Agriculture, Global Precision Agriculture Market and Global Livestock Monitoring Market sizes, their growth and trends and the key players of each market with the aim to understand the dynamics, opportunities and challenges within the Agriculture industry.

3.1.2.2 Market Definition and Scope

Agriculture is the practice of cultivating plants, raising animals, and producing food, fibre, and other products for human consumption, use, or trade. It's one of the oldest and most essential activities for human survival and economic development. Agriculture involves various processes, techniques, and technologies to grow crops and raise livestock efficiently (Harris and Fuller, 2014). Given the impending challenges faced by the agriculture and food sector, including factors like climate change, population expansion, technological advancements, and the

condition of natural resources, the utilisation of digital technologies across various stages of the agriculture supply chain is of paramount importance. This entails implementing technologies such as farm machinery automation, sensor integration, remote satellite data utilisation, artificial intelligence, and machine learning for enhanced crop and water monitoring, as well as ensuring traceability for agricultural food products (Ben Ayed and Hanana, 2021).

3.1.2.3 Market Size and Growth

The Global Agriculture Market size is expected to expand at a CAGR of 9.1% from 2023 to 2027 reaching a market size of \$ 19007.8 billion. The constant increase of the world's population is leading to an increase in food demand and consequently, an urgent need for the overall industrial development of the agricultural sector (Maroli et al., 2021). As per the Agricultural Outlook jointly presented by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), projections reveal a 13% increase in global cereal production by 2027. To cater to the heightened population demands, there will be a necessity for amplifying crop production, farming activities, and trade capacities. Agribusiness companies are likely to intensify their acquisition of arable land to increase crop production. The presence and the activities by agricultural companies are expected to increase in order to meet the increased demand from farming activities and consequently increase their growth (Research and Markets, 2023).

Regarding the digital agriculture market, technological progress, waste reduction, resource optimization, maximising yields, and well-structured government policies are collectively raising awareness about digital agriculture. This heightened awareness is driving the increased adoption of digital agriculture practices. These trends represent significant factors within the global digital agriculture market, contributing to its anticipated growth. Additional forces behind the adoption of digital initiatives in agriculture include affordability, connectivity, availability, and supportive government policies. These factors influence the industry's digital transformation. Indeed, **the Global Digital Agriculture Market size is expected to expand at a CAGR of 10.5% from 2022 to 2027 reaching a market size of \$ 29.8 billion** (Figure 12). Technological progress, waste reduction and resource optimization, yield enhancement, and well-structured governmental policies are fostering an increased recognition of digital agriculture. These factors collectively contribute to the rising adoption of digital agriculture practices. These noteworthy trends are driving growth in the global digital agriculture market (Allied Market Research, 2021).

Figure 12 Digital Agriculture Market size, 2022 to 2030 (USD Billion)

(source: <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/digital-agriculture-market-235909745.html>)

Precision agriculture represents a contemporary method of managing farms and agricultural activities that leverages information technology to guarantee precise delivery of necessary elements to crops and soil, promoting their optimal health and productivity. The overarching objective of precision agriculture is to achieve profitability, sustainability, and environmental preservation (Allied Market Research, 2018). The **Global Precision Agriculture Market size is expected to expand at a CAGR of 14.95% from 2021 to 2030 reaching a market size of \$ 19.24 billion (Straits Research, n.d.)**. The hardware segment held the dominant position in the broader smart agriculture market in 2020. This dominance is projected to continue over the forecast period due to the rising adoption of hardware, particularly in developing countries. Hardware plays a critical role in ensuring the effective operation of smart agriculture market software, thereby contributing to the growth of the precision agriculture market. Conversely, the service segment is anticipated to experience the most substantial growth in the forthcoming years. This trend is attributed to the increased integration of precision agriculture software into modern farming practices. As a result, there is a heightened demand for various services, including system integration and managed services. Many countries are embracing these services to streamline all agricultural and farming tools. This encompasses activities such as yield monitoring, field mapping, and weather forecasting, all of which collectively enhance overall farming productivity (Allied Market Research, 2021).

Livestock management, referred to as livestock monitoring or precision livestock farming, involves the utilisation of Internet of Things (IoT) devices to track and oversee the well-being of livestock, primarily cattle. This technology empowers farmers to remotely monitor their farm animals, allowing for more attentive supervision from a distance (Acumen, 2022). **The Global Livestock Monitoring Market size is expected to expand at a CAGR of 11% from 2022 to 2030 reaching a market size of \$ 3.7 Billion (Markets and Markets, 2022)** (Figure 13).

Figure 13 Livestock Monitoring Market

(source: <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/livestock-monitoring-market-72634532.html>)

Market growth is notably propelled by an upswing in cases of chronic animal diseases and disorders. Additionally, the mounting imperative to meet global food requirements is fuelling the market's expansion. The demand surge for animal-derived products, encompassing meat, milk, and dairy goods, is projected to persist until 2030 (Acumen, 2022). The growth trajectory is further supported by the augmented adoption of technology-driven farming solutions, ongoing technological advancements, innovative tool introductions, the unpredictability linked to climate shifts, and genetic variables, all collectively creating favourable market prospects. However, there are challenges to address. Notably, the high capital investments required, coupled with the agricultural sector's fragmentation, pose challenges. Issues of determining hygienic conditions and the absence of favourable reimbursement structures in developing and underdeveloped economies also add complexity. Furthermore, market growth may be hindered by inadequate network infrastructure in remote communities and the lack of standardised protocols for data processing and aggregation. Overall, the market's potential is driven by numerous growth factors, while challenges necessitate strategic considerations to ensure sustainable and widespread development (Acumen, 2022).

3.1.2.4 Competitive Landscape

- **Global Agriculture Market:** The key players in the Global Agriculture Market include Cargill Incorporated, Dairy Farmers of America, Bayer AG, WH Group Limited, Bunge Limited, Wens Foodstuff Group Co. Ltd., Charoen Pokphand Foods PCL, Corteva Inc., Olam International, and Land O'Lakes Inc. and others (The Business, 2023).
- **Digital Agriculture Market:** Key players in the digital agriculture market include among other CISCO Systems, Inc. (US), IBM Corporation (US), Accenture (Ireland), Deere & Company (US), Trimble INC. (US), DeLaval (Sweden), AKVA Group (Norway), Hexagon AB (Sweden), DJI (China), Epicor Software

Corporation (US), Vodafone Group PLC, Bayer Cropscience AG (Germany), TELUS AGRICULTURE (Canada), Small Robot Company (England), Zemdirbiu Konsultacijos UAB (England), Raven Industries (US), Gamaya (Switzerland), AGCO Corporation (US), PrecisionHawk (US), Agreena (Denmark), Ceres Imagine (US), Agricultural Consulting Services (US), EC2CE (Spain), Eurofins Scientific (France) and Arable (US) (Markets and Markets, 2022).

- **Precision Agriculture Market:** Key players in the precision agriculture market are Deere & Company, CropMetrics LLC, Trimble Navigation Limited, CropX, AgSmarts Inc, AgSense LLC, AGCO Corporation, DICKEY-john, Monsanto Company, Ag Leader Technology (Straits Research, 2023).
- **Livestock Monitoring Market:** Some prominent players in the global livestock monitoring market include GEA Group Aktiengesellschaft, Afimilk Ltd., DeLaval, Sensaphone, Intervet Inc., a subsidiary of Merck & Co. Inc., BouMatic, Dairymaster, Lely, Fancom BV, Fullwood Packo (Grand View Research, n.d.).

The market analysis of the Agricultural sector underscores its critical role in global food production and the broader economy. With a growing global population, the demand for agricultural products continues to rise, creating opportunities and challenges for this industry. Sustainability has become a central theme, driving the adoption of eco-friendly practices, organic farming, and the integration of technology to optimise resource use. The competitive landscape features a mix of traditional and modern farming approaches, with a growing emphasis on supply chain resilience and food security. As the agricultural sector navigates issues like climate change, resource scarcity, and evolving consumer preferences, innovation and sustainability will remain pivotal factors influencing its future growth and development.

3.1.3 Forestry

3.1.3.1 Use Case(s), services and related sectors

The **Use Case No 4 in Lithuania** belongs to the Forestry sector. The services the use case provides are **(i) Precision Agriculture** and **(ii) Forest Management**. Despite our efforts, we couldn't locate any pre-existing market analysis **on digital connectivity in the Forestry sector**, the XGain project recognises the importance of internet connectivity and how challenging could be the lack of a 5G network in the assessment and improvement of health and nutrient composition in farms. XGain offers hybrid solutions of local and edge- or cloud-based solutions to efficiently handle data transfer from areas with limited internet connectivity, such as agricultural fields or forests. The added value is to enable near-in-situ analysis and near-real-time decision-making, reducing the use of chemicals and fertilisers in agriculture and improving the efficiency and rapid evaluation of some forest monitoring data.

Subsequently, we present an alternative market analysis. While it may not align perfectly, this approach can yield valuable insights for gaining an understanding of the market and evaluating its growth potential.

Our research focused **on Global Forestry and Logging Market and Global Precision Forestry market** sizes, their growth and trends and the key players of each market with the aim to understand the dynamics, opportunities and challenges within the Forestry industry.

3.1.3.2 Market Definition and Scope

Forestry is the practice and science of managing, cultivating, and conserving forests and wooded areas for various purposes. It encompasses a wide range of activities aimed at sustainable forest management, ecosystem preservation, and the utilisation of forest resources. Forestry plays a critical role in providing timber, non-timber

forest products, ecosystem services, and contributing to environmental conservation (MarketResearch.com, n.d.). Obtaining precise data regarding the composition, structure, volume, growth, and coverage of forests is crucial for practising sustainable forest management (Shao 2012). In recent years, the worldwide forestry sector has demonstrated consistent growth, driven by rising requirements for commodities like paper, furniture, and bioenergy.

3.1.3.3 Market Size and Growth

The Global Forestry and Logging Market size is expected to expand at a CAGR of 80% from 2021 to 2028 reaching a market size of \$ 59,062.58 billion (Data Bridge Market Research,2021). The forestry industry's future prospects are optimistic, anticipating sustained expansion in the forthcoming years. Anticipated growth includes heightened demand for items like paper, furniture, and bioenergy, along with a parallel surge in interest for sustainable forestry practices and reforestation initiatives. The expansion of the forestry industry is projected to be propelled by a growing need for sustainable forestry practices, coupled with elevated investments in reforestation endeavours (Industry Growth Trends, 2023). The forest industry holds a significant position within the global economy and exerts substantial impacts on both our daily lives and the environment in which we reside. As digital technologies rapidly progress, industries are undergoing a transformation from conventional, isolated systems of manufacturing, logistics, decision-making, and services to a more interconnected and intelligent approach to industrialization (Feng and Audy, 2020).

Precision forestry involves strategically planning, executing, and overseeing forest management activities and operations and encompasses leveraging advanced technology to efficiently tackle time-intensive tasks within the forestry domain. The goal is to enhance the quality of wood products, minimise waste, boost profitability, and ensure the preservation of environmental quality (Allied Market Research, 2023). **The Global precision forestry market attained a value of \$ 4.73 billion in 2022 and it is expected to expand at a CAGR of 8.7% from 2023 to 2028 reaching a market size of \$ 7.81 billion (Expert Market Research, n.d.).** The global precision forestry market is poised for rapid growth in the foreseeable future. This surge can be attributed primarily to the increased adoption of cut-to-length harvesting technology, which streamlines tree-cutting processes. Moreover, the mounting demand for wood across diverse industry sectors is expected to fuel the expansion of the global precision forestry market. Governments backing for the adoption of contemporary forestry technologies as a measure to curb illegal logging is serving as an additional impetus for the expansion of the precision forestry market.

Key drivers contributing to this growth include the upward trajectory of mechanised forestry operations, reduced costs associated with cutting-edge monitoring and surveillance technologies, escalating demands for forestry products, and heightened governmental backing for implementing contemporary forestry techniques to combat illegal logging. However, obstacles such as high costs, limited awareness, and a dearth of skilled labour are projected to impede the potential growth of the global precision forestry market in the upcoming years. Additional factors that are poised to propel the global precision forestry market include a surge in construction activities, heightened timber demand from sawmills, augmented measures against illegal logging and deforestation, and favourable governmental policies promoting forest digitalization (Feng and Audy, 2020).

3.1.3.4 Competitive Landscape

- **Forestry and logging market:** The major players covered in the forestry and logging market are Weyerhaeuser Company, China Forestry Group Corporation, Rayonier Inc., PotlatchDeltic Corporation, Forestry Corporation of NSW, Jilin Forest Industry Group Co., Ltd., Tilhill Forestry, Rayonier Inc., Get It

Filed, LLC. , CatchMark Timber Trust, Inc., Hancock Victorian Plantations, IBISWorld, Greater Khingan Mountains Forestry Group, China Jilin Forestry Industry Group Co., Ltd., Singla Timbers, Oji Holdings Corporation, EGGER Group, RTS Forestry, James Jones and Sons Limited, Metsähallitus Forestry Ltd., among other domestic and global players (Data Bridge Market Research, 2021).

- **Precision Forestry Market:** Key players in the precision forestry market are among others Deere & Company, Ponsse PLC, Komatsu Forest, Treemetrics Ltd., Rottne Industri AB, Sampo-Rosenlew Oy, Tigercat International Inc (Expert Market Research, n.d.).

The market analysis of the Forestry sector reveals an industry that plays a crucial role in global environmental conservation and the production of renewable resources. Forestry encompasses a wide range of activities, including timber harvesting, pulp and paper production, and conservation efforts. The competitive landscape features both large-scale forest management companies and smaller, specialised operations, all working toward balancing economic viability with environmental responsibility. As global concerns about deforestation and climate change intensify, the forestry sector is evolving to meet these challenges, emphasising sustainable practices, reforestation efforts, and conservation initiatives to secure its future and benefit the planet.

3.1.4 Environmental monitoring

3.1.4.1 Use Case(s), services and related sectors

Environmental monitoring sector will be explored through the activities of **Use Cases No 1, No 3 and No 5**, which are placed in **Spain, UK and Croatia** respectively. The services those use cases provide are **(i) Drones operation in rural areas** and **(ii) additional services with high data rate** in Use Case 1 - Spain, **(iii) Precision Agriculture** and **(iv) Tourism** in Use Case 3 - UK and **(v) Water quality monitoring** and **(vi) Remote oyster farming** in Use Case - 5 in Croatia. While our search efforts did not yield any existing market analysis specifically focused on **digital connectivity within the Environmental Monitoring sector**, the XGain project is acutely aware of the significance of robust ICT (Information and Communication Technology) infrastructure (e.g. EO sensors and cameras, edge services etc) recognising the challenges posed by the absence of connectivity in the environmental monitoring sector. XGain offers solutions that will help among others to increase the efficiency of farm operations, cost reduction, protect biodiversity and the environment.

Next, we offer an alternative market analysis. Although not an exact match, this approach can offer valuable insights for comprehending the market and assessing its growth potential.

Our research focused on **Global Environmental Monitoring Market** size, its growth and trends and the key players of the market with the aim to understand the dynamics, opportunities and challenges within the Environmental industry.

3.1.4.2 Market Definition and Scope

Environmental monitoring refers to the systematic process of observing, measuring, and assessing various aspects of the natural environment over time. The goal of environmental monitoring is to gather data and information about environmental conditions, changes, and trends in order to make informed decisions about resource management, policy development, and conservation efforts. Monitoring helps track the health of ecosystems, identify pollution or degradation, and assess the effectiveness of interventions (Artiola et al., 2004). Enormous amounts of data are collected from IoT devices linked through communication technologies. This data extraction process plays a key role in enhancing environmental performance (Maroli et al., 2021).

3.1.4.3 Market Size and Growth

The Global Environmental Monitoring Market size is expected to expand at a CAGR of 8.2% from 2021 to 2030 reaching a market size of \$ 43.48 billion (Allied Market Research, 2021) (Figure 14). Environmental monitoring entails assessing the environmental quality to mitigate the risk of pollution. The fundamental objective of an environmental monitoring system is to oversee diverse environmental variables like temperature, humidity, airflow, and smoke. It also involves maintaining comprehensive records of these factors while simultaneously employing a high-quality camera for live video streaming. The market is experiencing growth due to heightened health concerns and a surge in fatalities attributed to the escalation of pollution levels.

Figure 14 Environmental monitoring market by application

(source: <https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/environmental-monitoring-market>)

Additionally, the necessity for improved resource management acts as a driving force. Moreover, the ongoing deployment of environmental monitoring sensors and the advancement of eco-friendly industries are contributing to market expansion. Nonetheless, market growth faces hindrances such as elevated product costs and the gradual execution of pollution control reforms in emerging nations. However, a promising outlook is anticipated with increasing business involvement and investments for the implementation of pollution monitoring. This trend is expected to unlock substantial opportunities for market expansion in the future (Markets and Markets, 2021) (Figure 15).

Figure 15 Environmental monitoring market by product type

(source: <https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/environmental-monitoring-market>)

3.1.4.4 Competitive Landscape

- Environmental Monitoring Market:** The key players operating in the global environmental monitoring market include 3M, Danaher, Emerson Electric Co., General Electric, Honeywell International Inc., Merck KGaA , Siemens AG, Teledyne Technologies Incorporated, TE Connectivity Ltd. and Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc. These players have adopted various strategies to increase their market penetration and strengthen their foothold in the environmental monitoring industry (Allied Market Research, 2021).

The market analysis of the Environmental Monitoring sector underscores its critical role in addressing pressing global environmental challenges. This industry has witnessed significant growth due to increasing awareness of environmental issues, stringent regulations, and the **need for real-time data** to mitigate environmental risks. The competitive landscape features established players alongside innovative startups, all striving to provide **advanced monitoring solutions through the integration of IoT** (Internet of Things), **remote sensing**, and **data analytics**. As environmental concerns intensify, the Environmental Monitoring sector is poised for continuous growth and innovation, playing a pivotal role in safeguarding the planet's ecosystems and human well-being.

3.1.5 e-Health

3.1.5.1 Use Case(s), services and related sectors

The **Use case No 2 in Greece** belongs to the e-Health sector. The services the use case provides are **(i) an e-Health robot that will act as a virtual caregiver for the elderly**, **(ii) High data rate services** and **(iii) Tourism**. Even if we couldn't locate any **existing market analysis on digital connectivity in the e-Health sector**, the XGain project recognises the importance of adequate internet connectivity and how challenging could be the everyday life for elderly people especially when they live in remote areas. The XGain offers services aiming to improve the well-being of the elderly by providing monitoring and advice (e.g. cognitive exercises, nutritional guidance, physical exercises, and social recommendations).

Subsequently, we present an analogous market analysis as an alternative. Although it may not be an exact match, this approach can offer valuable insights for comprehending the market and evaluating its growth potential.

Our research focused on **Global Digital Health Market**, **Global mHealth market** and **Healthcare companion robots market** sizes, their growth and trends and the key players of each market with the aim to understand the dynamics, opportunities and challenges within the e-Health industry.

3.1.5.2 Market Definition and Scope

E-health, refers to the use of digital technologies and electronic communication tools to provide healthcare services, manage health information, and improve the overall health sector. E-health encompasses a wide range of applications and solutions that leverage technology to enhance healthcare delivery, patient engagement, and medical information management (Kreps and Neuhauser, 2010) (Tavares, 2018). Furthermore, solutions like mHealth applications and telemedicine services aid in remotely monitoring diverse health metrics at home, thus eradicating the necessity for hospital appointments (Bardaro et al., 2021; Markets and Markets, 2021).

3.1.5.3 Market Size and Growth

The Global Digital Health Market size is expected to expand at a CAGR of 17.9% from 2021 to 2030 reaching a market size of \$767,718.9 million. The expansion of the global digital health market is primarily propelled by elevated demand for remote monitoring services. Moreover, increased funding from both private and government entities for mHealth startups, the escalation in chronic disease prevalence, and the integration of advanced technologies within the healthcare sector are significant factors driving this growth. Nevertheless, apprehensions regarding the assurance of regulatory compliance are projected to limit the growth of the digital health market throughout the forecast period (Allied Market Research, 2021).

Mobile health (mHealth) describes the use of mobile devices for healthcare purposes and it covers an extensive array of mobile health applications and services that utilise mobile technology to enhance health results, improve the provision of healthcare, and enable individuals to manage their own well-being effectively. **The Global mHealth market size is expected to expand at a CAGR of 18% from 2023 to 2032 reaching a market size of \$370.7 billion.** The growth of the mHealth market size is driven by rise in geriatric population along with chronic diseases (e.g. chronic cardiac diseases such as heart attack, hypertension, and stroke), which further increase the demand for mHealth devices to monitor the heart health of patients. Furthermore, the adoption of mobile health applications (mHealth apps) and interconnected devices empowers individuals dealing with diabetes to track their blood glucose levels. As a result, the anticipated rise in diabetes prevalence is projected to amplify the expansion of the mHealth market segment. Moreover, the escalated utilisation of cutting-edge healthcare devices and technologies, encompassing mHealth solutions and wearable devices, aimed at augmenting operational efficiency, stands as a pivotal driver for the expansion of the mHealth market segment (Allied Market Research, 2023).

The advancement, uptake, and execution of a diverse array of novel eHealth/mHealth applications (such as online health information platforms, interactive electronic health records, customised health education initiatives, healthcare system portals etc) carry significant potential. These technologies hold the promise of augmenting both consumer and provider access to pertinent health information, elevating care quality, mitigating healthcare errors, fostering collaboration, and promoting the adoption of healthful behaviours (Kreps and Neuhauser, 2010).

The companion robot contributes to the improvement of well-being and overall quality of life through its range of assistance functionalities. Primarily, it offers cognitive assistance, aids in mobility, and facilitates relaxation. Furthermore, it plays a role in health monitoring and furnishes self-care support through interactive engagement

(Figure 16). **The Healthcare companion robots market attained a value of \$ 1.5 billion in 2022 and is expected to reach a compound annual growth rate of 17.8% from 2023 to 2030.** The increasing global elderly population coupled with a limited number of healthcare professionals available to cater to this demographic is projected to drive the demand for companion robots (Grand View Research, n.d.).

Figure 16 Healthcare companion robots market share by group

Advancements in medical robotics and the growing prevalence of disabilities are additional factors propelling market growth. Companion robots hold the potential to enhance the lives of individuals grappling with such challenges by offering assistance. The emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic has exerted a positive impact on market growth. Government-enforced lockdowns and social distancing measures have led to heightened social isolation and feelings of loneliness. This circumstance has bolstered the acceptance of companion robots as a means to bridge these gaps and alleviate loneliness, particularly among the elderly. These robots have also been employed to aid therapeutic interventions aimed at enhancing mental well-being and alleviating anxiety issues. Furthermore, they have found utility in remote health monitoring and medication management (Grand View Research, n.d.).

3.1.5.4 Competitive Landscape

- **Digital Health:** Key players operating in the global digital health market include Allscripts Healthcare Solution, Inc., Cerner Corporation, Cisco Systems, eCLINICALWORKS, General Electric company, Koninklijke Philips N.V., Honeywell International Inc., Mckesson Corporation, Siemens Healthcare AG, and Qualcomm technologies, Inc (Allied Market Research, 2021).
- **mHealth:** Major players in the mHealth market are Boston Scientific Corporation, DexCom, Inc., FITBIT, INC. (Google), Koninklijke Philips N.V., Medtronic plc, Omada Health, Omron Corporation, SAMSUNG ELECTRONICS CO., LTD., Teladoc Health, Inc., and Welldoc, Inc (Allied Market Research, 2021).
- **Healthcare companion robots:** The healthcare companion robots' market is experiencing growth driven by key players' implementation of diverse strategies, including product development and partnerships. As an illustration, in May 2018, Remi AI collaborated with Ikkiworks to develop the AI language component for the world's pioneering companion robot designed for ill children. Noteworthy participants in the global healthcare companion robots market encompass: Blue Frog Robotics & Buddy

ASUS, Intuition Robotics, inGen Dynamics, PARO Robots U.S., Inc., No Isolation, Luvozo, Honda Robotics, Hanson Robotics, Ubtech, Emotix, Jibo(Grand View Research, n.d.).

The market analysis of the e-health sector reveals a rapidly evolving landscape at the intersection of healthcare and digital technology. E-health, driven by the increasing adoption of digital health solutions and the demand for convenient, accessible healthcare services, has experienced exponential growth. The competitive landscape is marked by established healthcare institutions, tech giants, and startups, all striving to provide innovative solutions that enhance patient care, improve clinical outcomes, and streamline healthcare delivery. As the healthcare industry embraces digital transformation, the e-health sector is poised for continued expansion and innovation, offering promising opportunities to improve healthcare accessibility, affordability, and quality.

3.1.6 e-Governance

3.1.6.1 Use Case(s), services and related sectors

The **Use case No 2** in **Greece** belongs to the e-Governance sector. The services the use case provides are **(i) an e-Health robot that will act as a virtual caregiver for the elderly, (ii) High data rate services** and **(iii) Tourism**. Although we were unable to find **any existing market analysis on digital connectivity in the e-Governance sector**, the XGain recognises the importance of ICT infrastructure to deliver public services, make them more accessible, responsive, and citizen-centric, improve healthcare services and education. XGain offers a solution aiming to support the social interaction of people, increase e-literacy and digital skills, upgrade network quality, advertise and showcase the tourist product.

Although it may not be an exact match, we are presenting a similar market analysis as an alternative next. This approach can yield valuable insights for comprehending the market and assessing its growth potential.

Our research focused on **Global e-Governance Market Industry** and **Global Smart Government Market** sizes, their growth and trends and the key players of each market with the aim to understand the dynamics, opportunities and challenges within the e-Governance industry.

3.1.6.2 Market Definition and Scope

E-governance, refers to the use of digital technologies, information and communication technologies (ICTs), and online platforms to enhance the delivery of government services, improve interactions between the government and citizens, and promote transparency, efficiency, and accountability in governance processes (eGovernment and Digital Public Services, 2023; Srivastava, 2015).

3.1.6.3 Market Size and Growth

The Global e-Governance Market Industry is expected to expand at a CAGR of 13.2% from 2023 to 2032 reaching a market size of \$15.36 billion. The expansion of the market is being propelled by the increasing utilisation of government regulations and the establishment of business partnerships, which serve as key drivers for its growth (Market Research Future, 2023). The increasing volume of data and the adoption of intelligent technologies are propelling the CAGR of the e-governance market. A primary driving force behind this market growth is the ability of citizens to engage with government services in innovative ways due to the growing presence of smart technologies implemented by governments worldwide. Several factors contribute to the expansion of government data generation, including the growing census data resulting from population growth, the introduction of new policies and initiatives, cross-regional collaborations, and a rise in GDP due to the emergence of new businesses. While legacy systems dependent on physical hardware might be efficient, their

capacity is finite. As a result, e-governance is gaining increasing popularity (Market Research Future, 2023). As governments progress towards achieving e-governance maturity, there is an anticipated upward trajectory in government IT budgets. Within these budgets, a significant portion is projected to be allocated to ICT services. Among the various components, the sector with the most substantial growth is expected to be ICT software designed for online government functions, followed by services, networking, and hardware (Palanisamy 2004).

Smart government entails the utilisation of interconnected and intelligent information and communication technology (ICT) to streamline governmental and administrative operations. This encompassing framework includes endeavours like e-government, open-government initiatives, and the integration of big data and open data. It encompasses the strategic management of governmental and administrative functions in the era of the Internet of Things (IoT) and the Internet of Services. These components are based on the Internet of Systems, the Internet of People, and the Internet of Data. **The Global Smart Government Market is expected to expand at a CAGR of 19.4% from 2022 to 2031 reaching a market size of \$ 124.7 billion (Allied Market Research, 2022)** (Figure 17). The swift expansion of the market can be ascribed to positive government initiatives across the globe and the emergence of transformative technologies like artificial intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT). Additionally, the escalating demand for cloud computing, even from nations grappling with persistent data security and privacy concerns, is anticipated to provide an upswing to the market's growth. Furthermore, the increased extraction of data from diverse sources for subsequent digital transformation is also propelling market expansion within the forecast period. However, apprehensions regarding data breaches and privacy infringement are projected to impede the growth of the smart government market. The presence of hackers and the associated risks of data breaches are also expected to place limitations on the market's progress (Polaris, 2021).

Figure 17 Smart government market by type

(Source: <https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/smart-government-market-A07475>)

The COVID-19 situation has led to a heightened requirement for smart government services, along with an amplified need for existing services. Government entities were swiftly mobilised and dedicated to crafting tools, applications, and services to contribute to the battle against COVID-19. Among these newly introduced services

is the efficient distribution of food and essential goods to vulnerable populations, bolstered by the optimization of the supply chain through smart government interventions. Furthermore, due to the surge in unemployment and requests for social benefits, several Member States observed an uptick in online service utilisation, including digital identification and digital signatures (Polaris, 2021).

3.1.6.4 Competitive Landscape

- **e-Governance Market Industry:** Leading market players are channelling investments and resources into research and development endeavours to expand their range of products. This concerted effort is anticipated to further fuel the growth of the E-Governance market (Market Research Future, 2023). Additionally, market contenders and producers are embracing a range of strategic initiatives to enhance their global footprint. These significant market advancements encompass novel product introductions, contract agreements, mergers and acquisitions, heightened investments, and collaborative ventures with similar organisations. Major players in the E-Governance market include Oracle Corporation (US), EMC Corporation (US), Metric Stream Inc. (US), IBM Corporation (US), Microsoft Corporation (US), SAS Institute Inc. (US), Fidelity National Information Services Inc. (US), Thomson and Reuters Corporation (US), SAP SE (Germany), Wolters Kluwer NV (Netherlands) (Market Research Future, 2023).
- **Smart governance:** Key players operating in the smart government market include ABB Ltd., Amazon Web Services, Inc., Avaya Inc., Capgemini S.A., Cisco Systems, Inc., CitizenLab, Decidim, Huawei Technologies Co., Ltd., Imex Systems Inc., Nokia Corporation. These players have implemented diverse tactics to enhance their market reach and strengthen their position in the industry (Allied Market Research, 2022).

The market analysis of the e-governance sector underscores its pivotal role in transforming public administration and service delivery through digital technology. E-governance, fueled by the increasing demand for efficient and transparent government operations, has gained prominence globally. The competitive landscape features established e-governance providers, tech companies, and specialised startups, all contributing to the evolution of digital governance. As the digital era continues to redefine citizen expectations and government operations, the e-governance sector is poised for sustained growth and innovation, empowering governments to deliver public services more efficiently and transparently.

3.1.7 Tourism

3.1.7.1 Use Case(s), services and related sectors

Tourism sector will be explored through the activities of **Use Cases No 1, No 2 and No 3** which are placed in **Spain, Greece and UK** respectively. The services those use cases provide are **(i) Drones operation in rural areas** and **(ii) Additional services with high data rate** in Use Case 1 - Spain, **(iii) E-Health robot that will act as a virtual caregiver for the elderly**, **(vi) High data rate services** and **(v) Tourism** in Use Case 2 - Greece and **(vi) Precision Agriculture** and **(vii) Tourism** in Use Case 3 - UK. Although we were unable to find any **existing market analysis on digital connectivity in the Tourism sector**, the XGain project recognises the importance of internet connectivity in touristic areas and how it increases the competitiveness and business sustainability of the sector. XGain offers a solution (e.g. cameras, routers, edge devices) to upgrade network quality and speed for a positive impact for tourism sectors, advertise and showcase the tourist product enhancing rural tourism.

Subsequently, we present an analogous market analysis as an alternative. Although it may not be an exact match, this approach can offer valuable insights for comprehending the market and evaluating its growth potential.

Our research focused on **Global Tourism Market**, **Global Rural Tourism Market** and **Global Augmented reality and Virtual reality market** sizes, their growth and trends and the key players of each market with the aim to understand the dynamics, opportunities and challenges within the Tourism industry.

3.1.7.2 Market Definition and Scope

Tourism refers to the activity of people travelling to destinations outside their usual environment for leisure, recreation, business, or other purposes. It involves a wide range of activities, services, and industries that cater to travellers' needs, enhance their experiences, and contribute to economic and cultural exchanges between different regions and countries. Tourism is a dynamic and evolving industry that plays a significant role in global connectivity, economic development, and cultural exchange. It presents opportunities for personal enrichment, economic growth, and the preservation of natural and cultural heritage.

3.1.7.3 Market Size and Growth

According to United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) data, world tourism visitors reached 1.3 billion in 2001, while in 2021, it is estimated that 2.3 billion tourists have travelled. Tourists do not only travel conventionally but also online or using the internet. Developments in information technology make tourism move rapidly (Roziqin et al., 2023).

The Global Tourism Market size is expected to expand at a CAGR of 5% from 2022 to 2032 reaching a market size of \$ 17.1 Trillion. The global tourism market is set to experience growth driven by emerging trends like adventure tourism and art tourism (Future Market Insights, n.d.). These trends are expected to contribute to the expansion of the market. The utilisation of tourism websites plays a crucial role in efficiently managing and capitalising on various forms of tourism experiences. Cultural and pilgrimage tourism are witnessing remarkable growth in Asia, Africa, and South America, while adventure and ecological tourism are the rapidly advancing sectors in North America and Europe. The occurrence of disease outbreaks like Ebola, SARS, and COVID in specific countries, coupled with geopolitical tensions, is exerting a substantial influence on the potential opportunities within the global tourism market. The global tourism market exhibits a state of low concentration, owing to the presence of numerous international and local participants. The market structure of global tourism is characterised by a high degree of fragmentation (Future Market Insights, n.d.) (Figure 18).

Figure 18 Global tourism industry market share (in %), segmented by region, 2035

(source: <https://www.researchnester.com/reports/tourism-industry-market/109>)

Rural tourism refers to the practice of tourists visiting and engaging with rural areas, countryside regions, villages, and remote locations for leisure, recreation, and cultural experiences. It offers travellers an opportunity to escape urban environments and immerse themselves in natural landscapes, local traditions, and the authentic lifestyles of rural communities. Rural tourism contributes to the development of rural economies, supports cultural heritage, and provides travellers with authentic and enriching experiences away from the hustle and bustle of urban life. It allows for a deeper connection to nature, traditions, and local communities (Rosalina et al., 2021). **The Global Rural Tourism Market size is expected to expand at a CAGR of 6.8% from 2023 to 2033 reaching a market size of \$ 198.3 billion (Future Market Insights. n.d.).** Rural tourism is among the burgeoning trends within the tourism industry, offering substantial backing to a country's primary sector while simultaneously contributing to the development of rural and remote areas. Rural tourism provides urban travellers with an opportunity to break away from urban routines and rediscover the charms of rural landscapes. Participating in activities on agricultural farms and in fields, along with exploring rural lifestyles, has evolved into a trend that entices travellers to engage in rural tourism experiences. Ultimately, this trend contributes significantly to the overall expansion of the tourism industry, driven by the income generated from rural tour activities (Writer, 2023).

Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) are rapidly emerging technologies that are increasingly accessible to consumers (Institute of Entrepreneurship Development, 2021). These technologies have also found their place within the realm of digital advancements in the field of tourism. In a fiercely competitive and thriving industry, the integration of AR and VR applications is essential. These state-of-the-art technologies play a pivotal role in enticing a larger customer base. The trends of AR and VR digital innovations offer travellers an unparalleled and immersive experience. Notably, hotels are leveraging VR to present their rooms to prospective clients. This dynamic medium surpasses static photographs or videos, enabling users to navigate spaces and interact with their surroundings as if they were physically present. Moreover, the realm of Virtual Reality grants individuals the ability to virtually explore the world without leaving their homes, courtesy of specialised VR goggles that transport users to any destination on the planet (Ozdemir 2021) (Katkuri, 2019). **The Global Augmented reality and Virtual reality market size is expected to expand at a CAGR of 25.3% from 2022 to 2027 reaching a market size of 114.5 billion (Figure 19).**

Figure 19 Global Augmented and Virtual reality market trends

(source: <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/augmented-reality-virtual-reality-market-1185.html>)

The growth trajectory of the AR and VR market is primarily steered by the escalating demand for mobile and handheld devices, coupled with the widespread utilisation of head-mounted displays (HMD). Furthermore, the increasing investments in research and development activities are serving as a catalyst for augmenting the market value of AR and VR technologies (Acumen, 2022). However, barriers such as limited understanding, software privacy apprehensions, and the high cost of ARVR technology might restrain the augmented and virtual reality market's growth. A persistent trend within the industry involves the application of AR/VR technology in diverse domains like live presentations, seminars, surgical procedures, video gaming, military operations, and 3D modelling. Moreover, the growing embrace of ARVR technology across various sectors, including healthcare, education, aerospace, military and security, digital manufacturing, and entertainment, is projected to significantly propel the expansion of this market in the forthcoming years (Acumen, 2022).

The Global AR/VR in Travel & Tourism Market is poised to experience a substantial Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) between 2022 and 2027 (Global Market Estimates, 2023). Throughout this projected period, the market's growth is expected to be propelled by a rising desire for travel and tourism services across various regions, coupled with heightened investments in AR/VR technologies within the travel and tourism sector. These investments aim to amplify the appeal of their offerings and services, contributing to the surge in market demand. VR technology in the realm of travel and tourism holds significant potential as a marketing tool, facilitating heightened consumer awareness and robust marketing campaigns geared towards revenue growth. Concurrently, the augmented reality (AR) endeavours undertaken by the tourism industry primarily focus on enhancing visitor experiences by furnishing informative content to enrich their understanding of tourist attractions. This augmentation not only enhances the overall tourist experience but also elevates leisure prospects. The escalating desire for travel and tourism experiences, coupled with the extensive application of AR and VR across diverse domains like planning, management, advertising, information dissemination, recreation, education, accessibility, and heritage preservation, is propelling the demand for AR/VR technologies within the travel and tourism sector (Global Market Estimates, 2023).

The prominent advantages derived from the utilisation of AR travel applications involve the transformation and enhancement of users' perceptions of their immediate physical environment. The engagement of AR/VR technology fosters interactive and immersive virtual experiences for users. Projections suggest that the count of AR users is anticipated to reach 2.4 billion by 2023. Travel agencies are poised to leverage this prevailing trend to craft distinct customer offerings that capitalise on these technologies (ReporterLinker, 2023).

3.1.7.4 Competitive Landscape

- **Tourism Market:** Some of the players in the global tourism market are AirBnB Inc., Aban Offshore Ltd., Accor Group, Crown Ltd., Balkan Holidays Ltd., Fred Harvey Company and G Adventures (Future Market Insights, n.d.).
- **Rural Tourism:** The most dominant key players/manufacture in rural tourism industry are Farm to Farm, Agri Tourism Development, Liberty Hill Farm, Stita, GTI Travel, Heartland Travel and Tours, AgriProFocus, Cape AgriTours, Rural Tours, Meru Agro, Cyprus Agrotourism, Agrotours, PRTC, Zoobox, Outdooractive (TheExpressWire, 2022).
- **AR/VR market:** Google (US), Microsoft (US), Sony Corporation (Japan), Samsung Electronics (South Korea), HTC (Taiwan), Apple Inc., (US) are among the major market players in the global platform that lead the market growth of the global AR/VR in Travel & Tourism market. (Markets and Markets, 2022).

The market analysis of the tourism sector reveals a vibrant and ever-evolving industry that spans the globe, playing a significant role in economic development and cultural exchange. Sustainability and responsible tourism have become central themes, with travellers increasingly seeking eco-friendly and socially responsible travel options. The competitive landscape features a multitude of stakeholders, including hotels, airlines, tour operators, and online travel agencies, all vying for a share of the tourism market. As the global appetite for travel continues to grow, the tourism sector is poised for ongoing expansion and adaptation, with a focus on enhancing visitor experiences and minimising the environmental impact of travel.

3.2 Existing Business Models in remote areas

3.2.1 Broadband Business Models

The main reasons for not providing broadband access to rural areas are rather commercial than technical; the most common business model for providing connectivity until now is the 'Vertically Integrated Operator' model, in which the operator designs, builds, operates, and maintains the whole telecommunication network.

Considering that rural areas have some characteristics such as low population density, lack of backbone infrastructure and landscape variation, the cost of connecting these areas is considerably higher compared to urban ones and thus, not attractive for investment.

Considering a more liberative model that has been introduced the recent years mostly in fibre deployments, splits the network into three layers: passive equipment, active equipment and services, could indeed introduce new business models for the actors, introducing three new roles:

- the physical infrastructure owner that owns and maintains the passive infrastructure;
- the network provider that operates the active equipment;
- the service provider that delivers the service to end-users.

Business models ranging from an actor that takes all three roles to models that all roles are undertaken from different actors could be in place. For the latter, an open network model in which the infrastructure is open to all market participants in equal terms is achieved. In order to allow a number of smaller entities to enter the market along with local communities, with aim to promote the cooperation among actors, layer split is often used such as:

Passive Layer Open Model (PLOM) in which an entity (e.g., a local cooperative, or a private investor, depending on the investment model chosen) builds and operates passive infrastructure to be made available to all market actors under fair and non-discriminatory conditions;

Active-Layer Open Model (ALOM) in which one entity deploys and operates the passive and active layer (hence acting as an integrated physical infrastructure and network provider);

Three-Layer Open Model (3LOM) in which the roles of physical infrastructure provider, network and service provider are explicitly separated.

Another rising model already adopted by several countries such as Croatia, Lithuania, Greece and Austria, is the Public Private Partnership (PPP), that is a co-operation model in which the public actor usually undertakes a part of the construction cost while the private part is responsible for the operation and maintenance of the infrastructure. Alternatively, the USA's co-operation model is widely adapted - over 750 communities have built their own networks using that approach, involving the sharing of cost and/or revenues.

3.2.2 Financial tools and Models for tying rural and remote areas together

ICT development financing methods have changed throughout time. Prior to 2002, the required infrastructure investment outlays were substantially modest, and speech technology was still the primary focus. Today, however, the situation is much more complicated. In contrast to the past, when services were provided by large organisations, today's economy is heavily reliant on small and medium-sized businesses. Different finance methods must consequently be utilised to fund projects intended to expand rural residents' access to ICTs, as there is no universally applicable financing structure or model:

- **Public-utility financing model:** The municipality or government agency operates as an investor for an open-access network in urban and suburban roll-outs, securing early finance at cheaper rates for construction.
- **Direct investment model: the publicly-run municipal network model (public DBO).** In this model, the government entity initiates the development of a broadband network within a specific municipality, county, or region, a process often referred to as Design, Build, and Operate (DBO). The deployment is overseen and directly managed by the government authority. To accomplish this, either a newly established company or a specialised division within an existing utility company is tasked with deploying the network, either through direct implementation or standard procurement processes. Ownership of the network remains with the public authority, which is also responsible for its ongoing operation and maintenance. Subsequently, the network is typically made accessible to all market participants, operating as an open access network. The public authority or a dedicated entity assumes a substantial level of commitment and assumes all associated financial risks, while maintaining complete control over the network's design and its usage

- **Operator funding:** This happens when a network operator pays for infrastructure projects out of its own budget or with private capital. It is the most typical type of financing. However, with this kind of cash, investment is frequently confined to cities.
- **Universal service fund financing model:** Cost-sharing models include infrastructure pooling between rival businesses. Competition is usually hesitant to use these methods, though, which is where public money comes in.
- **Concession model: the privately-run municipal network model:** In this model, the public authority engages in a process known as public outsourcing or concession, wherein it outsources the construction and operation of a broadband network within a municipality, county, or region to a private entity. This private actor is granted a concession to operate the network for an extended period, typically ranging from twenty to thirty years. The contracted private firm's primary task is to establish an open, operator-neutral network, enabling various service providers to offer their services to end-users. While the public authority retains ownership of the passive infrastructure, it wields significant influence over the network's design and service provisioning. To ensure equitable and non-discriminatory conditions for all service providers, it is desirable that the private firm responsible for network construction and operation refrains from offering its own services, although this isn't always the case, often due to the limited availability of operator-neutral network providers and independent service providers in specific regions and a lack of awareness about this option. Throughout the contract period, the contracted firm assumes the financial investment, as well as the associated risks and revenues. Once the contract concludes, the network infrastructure remains under the control of the public authority, which may choose to renew the contract, enter into an agreement with another company, or potentially transition to a publicly managed municipal network model.
- **Community support model:** In this model, local residents take the lead in spearheading investments in broadband infrastructure through grassroots initiatives, reflecting a bottom-up approach. These community-led projects consistently yield notable success by fostering higher rates of end-user adoption and establishing financially sustainable ventures. The degree of competition within these initiatives varies, with some embracing an open network business model marked by robust competitive dynamics, while others function as fully integrated entities or engage in long-term service agreements with a single operator. Public authorities play a pivotal role in supporting these endeavors by offering co-financing, facilitating right-of-way (RoW) access, implementing regulatory frameworks, coordinating with other infrastructure development initiatives, and granting access to public infrastructure and critical points of presence for essential backhaul connections. Additionally, public authorities are instrumental in ensuring fair and impartial conditions for all operators seeking access to the shared infrastructure.
- **Operator subsidy model (gap-funding or private DBO):** In this model, the public authority does not directly engage in the broadband deployment projects within the region but rather provides subsidies to a specific market player to enhance their existing infrastructure. Typically, incumbent telecommunications operators and major alternative service providers own both the passive infrastructure and the active equipment while offering services to end-users under a vertically integrated framework. The public authority's role is to bridge the financial gap between what is commercially viable and the desired coverage objectives. This funding is provided in the form of grants to one or more private operators. This

model offers advantages in terms of streamlined contractual arrangements, the potential for relatively swift deployment, and shifting risks to the grant recipient or operator. However, public authorities do not generate financial returns from this approach; instead, they must contend with increasing funding requests for each subsequent deployment phase, resulting in higher investments than initially anticipated.

- **The neutral host model:** In this model, the public authority does not directly engage in the broadband deployment projects within the region but rather provides subsidies to a specific market player to enhance their existing infrastructure. Typically, incumbent telecommunications operators and major alternative service providers own both the passive infrastructure and the active equipment while offering services to end-users under a vertically integrated framework. The public authority's role is to bridge the financial gap between what is commercially viable and the desired coverage objectives. This funding is provided in the form of grants to one or more private operators. This model offers advantages in terms of streamlined contractual arrangements, the potential for relatively swift deployment, and shifting risks to the grant recipient or operator. However, public authorities do not generate financial returns from this approach; instead, they must contend with increasing funding requests for each subsequent deployment phase, resulting in higher investments than initially anticipated.

3.2.3 Partnerships to enable connectivity for rural and remote areas

When it comes to supporting initiatives intended to expand rural access to ICTs, partnerships are particularly helpful. Partnerships can ease the load on the government and even the private sector in establishing rural connections because they are not just financial in nature:

- **Public partnerships (PuP):** A partnership that is being employed in ICT development, as well as other disciplines, is a cooperation between a government body or public authority and another government body and/or public authority to promote, or in fact supply, services and/or facilities. Sometimes the aim is to impart technical knowledge and skills. Sometimes it is to split the expense of expensive initiatives in underdeveloped areas. Other local, regional, or state provincial organisations, school boards, parks boards, NGOs, unions, pension funds, professional associations, and community groups in emerging nations are examples of potential partners.
- **Public-private partnerships (PPPs):** They are the most typical kind of partnerships and have been used in many different economic areas. Large-scale domestic and international infrastructure projects are best suited for this kind of partnership. For instance, ICT content providers like Microsoft, Amazon, and Google are increasingly funding underwater cables and other ICT projects across a number of nations, either independently or in collaboration with government agencies and commercial ICT operators.
- **Private partnerships:** The ICT industry has made considerable use of private partnerships, which are started by for-profit parties without backing from public coffers, typically between ICT operators and financial institutions and insurance service providers. However, despite the fact that financial inclusion has increased dramatically as a result of collaborations between banks and ICT service providers, they do not often aim to provide universal access to broadband.

- **Intergovernmental partnerships:** Partnerships between international organisations, businesses, and governments are essential. These partnerships typically function as parts of regional organisations and focus more on developing policy and providing implementation guidance.

When implementing partnerships, it is vital to evaluate the implications of the various elements of these funding methods based on macroeconomic indicators of the relevant economy. The funding mechanism's adequacy in light of the macroeconomic conditions should be taken into account. PPPs are more useful and appropriate for projects requiring significant financial investments. It may be useful for smaller ICT initiatives to use in-country PuPs. (International Communication Union, 2021.)

3.2.4 Business model of an ISP: An example

As already mentioned, ISP companies do not have a standardised Business Model for providing digital connectivity in remote areas but instead, they adjust and customise their Business Model according to the specific requirements of each situation.

After a thorough desk research, we were able to find the **Business Model** of indicative **ISP companies** which operate in remote areas too and it is presented below (Figure 20). We share our discoveries regarding ISP companies that provide a wide range of products and services to both individual consumers and businesses, covering a variety of telecommunications and internet solutions.

In terms of business, the ISP company organises its operations into two operating segments:

- **Business Segment** – through which the company provides strategic, legacy and data integration products and services – including private line, ethernet, high-speed internet, colocation, and cloud hosting services – to small, medium and enterprise business, as well as wholesale and governmental customers; and
- **Consumer Segment** – through which the company provides strategic and legacy products and services to residential customers, including high-speed Internet, video and wireless services.

Figure 20 Standardised Business Model canvas of indicative ISP companies

Customer Segments

Companies offer a broad range of communications products and services to a broad customer base. The customers can be organised broadly into the following customer categories:

- **Consumers Customers**, comprising residential customers, including individuals and families across multiple consumer demographics;
- **Business Customers**, comprising small, medium and enterprise businesses, as well as government bodies, to which the company provides a range of commercial communications services; and
- **Wholesale Customers**, comprising various entities such as telecommunication companies, to which the company provides products and services on a wholesale basis.

Value Propositions

Companies offer value to its customers in the following ways:

- **Their size and industry standing**, being established as one of the foremost providers of telecommunications services, with significant market share and reputation for providing reliable services;
- **Their broad range of products and services**, offering a broad range of communications products and services to a diverse customer base, including for example high-speed internet, Ethernet, wireless, and cloud hosting services;

- **Their international reach**, serving customers across jurisdictions in Europe and other worldwide areas;
- **Their technologies and intellectual properties**, owning and utilising a number of proprietary and third-party technologies in their services, in order to ensure reliable and effective services; and
- **Their industry expertise and experience**, employing highly trained industry specialists, as well as a team of experienced industry professionals.

Channels

Companies operate their website, through which they provide information on their products and services, including their wholesale and business offerings. Consumers are able to order telephone, internet, and television bundles directly through their website. Companies also provide online customer portal, for both consumer and business customers, which allows customers to manage their accounts and make payments.

The companies make the majority of their sales through their in-house direct sales force. They maintain local offices in many of the larger population centres within their local service areas, through which their sales and customer support teams provide services. Companies also utilise their call centre personnel, as well as a number of channel partners, to promote sales of services.

The majority of ISP's services and products are provided using their own telecommunications network, which comprises a series of voice switches, data switches and routers, high-speed transport equipment, fibre-optic and copper cables, and other equipment.

Customer Relationships

The companies provide a range of products to their consumer customers on a self-service basis through their websites. This channel enables customers to browse products and bundles independently and order service packages without interacting directly with their sales personnel. Their online portal also allows consumers and business customers to manage their accounts and make payments independently.

The companies make the bulk of their sales through their direct sales force, which operates out of their offices and call centres. These sales personnel consult directly with customers, providing personalised advice and guidance on their various product and service offerings. The companies provide services primarily under fixed-term contracts.

Companies provide ongoing support to their customers, principally through their call centre-based customer support staff, customers are able to access tailored assistance from support personnel over the phone, by email, or via an online chat service. Companies additionally offer a range of support resources through their websites, including FAQs and product guides.

Customers are also able to follow companies' activities and interact with them directly through their social media accounts.

Key Activities

Companies align their operations into two core operating segments: Business, which provides strategic, legacy and data integration products and services to small, medium and enterprise business, as well as wholesale and governmental customers; and Consumer, which provides strategic and legacy products and services to residential customers.

Companies offer a wide range of communications products and services, including for example ethernet, colocation, hosting and broadband, data integration offerings, and cloud hosting services for business customers, and broadband and video, wireless, and local and long-distance voice services for consumers.

Key Partners

Companies manage a diverse partner ecosystem, ensuring that they are able to provide reliable and effective services. Their partners can be organised broadly into the following categories:

- **Supplier and Vendor Partners**, comprising suppliers of technologies, services, and equipment that are utilised across their two operating segments, as well as companies to which non-technical functions can be outsourced;
 - **Channel and Distribution Partners**, comprising various third parties involved in marketing and selling their products and services, including authorised resellers, and independent software vendors;
 - **Technology Partners**, comprising various technology companies, including original equipment manufacturers and systems integrators, that help to ensure their systems remain up to date and efficient;
 - **Telecommunications Partners**, comprising various companies and organisational bodies within the telecoms sector, with which they seek to identify and promote energy-efficient technologies and equipment; and
- Strategic and Alliance Partners**, comprising market leading companies across multiple industries, with which they collaborate on various joint marketing, branding, and other projects.

Key Resources

Their key resources are their technologies and intellectual properties, the equipment and supply chain, the websites and online client portals, the IT and communications infrastructure, the physical network infrastructure, the offices and call centres, the partnerships, and the personnel.

Both directly and through a number of subsidiaries, companies own numerous patents, trademarks, and other intellectual properties that are key in differentiating their offerings from those of their competitors.

Additionally, the companies own and or lease a number of physical properties that are important to their offerings. This notably includes their network of offices and call centres, as well as telephone lines, cables, and other network support assets.

Cost Structure

Companies incur costs in relation to the development of their technologies and intellectual properties, the procurement of equipment and services, the development of their online platforms, the maintenance of their IT and communications infrastructure, the development and maintenance of their physical network infrastructure, the operation of their offices and call centre assets, the management of their partnerships, the implementation of advertising and marketing campaigns, and the retention of their personnel.

Revenue Streams

Companies generate revenue through the provision of various communications products and services to consumers, businesses, and wholesale customers. Companies principally derive their revenue under fixed-term

service contracts, as well as through non-recurring services, such as inside wire installation, maintenance services, service activation and reactivation.

Following our extensive research efforts, we have arrived at a critical observation: there is a notable absence of established business models tailored for the crucial **last-mile digital connectivity in remote areas**. This observation marks a pivotal juncture where the XGain project, along with its Knowledge Facilitation Tool (KFT), steps in to address this gap. The project's mission is to develop inclusive, innovative and sustainable business models that are not only inclusive but can also solve the actual remote areas' pains based on the validation of XGain's real life use cases.

3.3 Internet Connectivity Value Chain Networks in Rural Areas

To develop an indicative value chain network for digital connectivity, a value network analysis was performed and is presented below. The methodology, which was adapted, included the analysis of the stakeholders (both internet consumers and internet providers, network and technology providers etc.) followed by their clustering into a set of stakeholders (Farmers, Agricultural Producers, Aquaculture producers etc., Mobile Network Providers, Internet Service Providers, Technology Providers, Government and Regulatory Bodies, Financial services, Research and Academic Institutions, Business and Industry Stakeholders) paving the way for the creation of the value chain network. This preliminary categorization is followed by a further clustering into the actors of the ecosystem (customer, partner, supplier, operator), as described in the Value Chain Network Kit, took place, according to their roles and stakes, as well as their relation and interconnection with the value streams of Last-Mile Connectivity (internet, money, services).

3.3.1 Clustering of Stakeholders

Clustering stakeholders is of utmost importance in the development of a robust and efficient value chain network for Last-Mile Internet Connectivity. By clustering these stakeholders into distinct categories based on their roles, interests, and contributions, we can gain a comprehensive understanding of the value creation network and identify key relationships and dependencies. This clustering approach allows us to uncover synergies, facilitate effective collaboration, and unlock the full potential of Internet-driven innovations in the use case sectors. Through a well-structured value chain network, we can harness the collective capabilities of stakeholders and drive positive impact across the entire use case ecosystems.

The methodology adapted towards the mapping and identification of the stakeholders, based on which the development of the main stakeholder's categories was built upon included the identification of the stakeholders involved at Internet Service level, including both Internet Consumers and Internet Providers in order to create the main categories, which represent all stakeholders. In the figure below (Figure 21), we present the clustering of all stakeholders participating in XGain's use cases.

Figure 21 Clustering of the Internet Connectivity' stakeholders

3.3.2 Development of the Value chain Network for Internet Connectivity in Rural Areas

The development of a robust and interoperable value chain network for Last-Mile Internet Connectivity holds paramount importance for sustainability. As all sectors increasingly embrace digitalization and data-driven solutions, the effective sharing and utilization of connectivity/data become essential for driving innovation,

sustainability, and productivity. By developing a well-structured value chain network, we can establish seamless interoperability among diverse stakeholders, including farmers, agri-tech and other related companies, research institutions, policymakers, and consumers. This network serves as a vital infrastructure for facilitating collaboration based on high-rate internet connectivity and thus data exchange, and value creation across all ecosystems. By leveraging the collective expertise and resources of these stakeholders, we can unlock new insights, enable evidence-based decision-making, and foster the development of innovative solutions that address key challenges in XGains' use case sectors. The value chain network not only promotes synergistic collaboration but also ensures the sustainable growth and resilience of Internet Connectivity for rural areas, contributing to more efficient, competitive, and sustainable sectors in Europe.

For the development of the value chain network of Last-Mile Internet Connectivity for rural areas, the philosophy of the Value Chain Network Kit was applied. More precisely, after the creation of the set of stakeholders, these were further distributed to the categories covering the Actors of the Value Creation Network, according to their relation and interconnection with the Value Streams. The Actors of the Value Creation Network consist of the categories customer, partner, supplier and operator, whereas the components of internet, money and services constitute the value streams.

The actors in the value creation network (customer, partners, suppliers, operators) and the value streams (Internet, money, services) are interconnected and mutually dependent within the value chain network. The operators provide the network, which is accessed and utilised by suppliers (ISPs) who in turn offer services to customers. The value streams (internet, money, services) flow between these actors, creating a collaborative ecosystem for value creation in the context of Internet connectivity. In other words, the value streams (internet, money, services) flow through and connect these actors in the value chain network, enabling the creation, exchange, and utilization of value within. Each actor's role and contribution determine how the value streams are leveraged, combined, and transformed to deliver value to the customer and other stakeholders involved in the Internet connectivity initiatives.

Customers: Customers are the end users or beneficiaries of the value created through the Internet connectivity space. They derive value from the services or solutions generated from the high-speed connectivity. Customers include farmers and agricultural producers, government and regulatory bodies, business and industry stakeholders, research and academic institutions (Table 3).

Table 3 Customers' Relation to Value Streams

Customers' Relation to Value Streams	
Internet	Customers access and utilise the network to add value to their business
Money	Customers may contribute financial resources to access or acquire connectivity services.
Services	Customers may receive specialised services, such as data analytics, customised solutions, or research findings, based on high-speed internet connectivity.

Partners: Partners refer to entities or organizations that collaborate and participate in the value chain network to support the Internet connectivity initiative. Partners can include technology and data providers, financial and insurance services, data intermediaries and service providers, government and regulatory bodies (Table 4).

Table 4 Partners' Relation to Value Streams

Partners' Relation to Value Streams	
Internet	Partners contribute their assets (e.g., IOT sensors, cameras etc.) to the shared network, enriching the available connectivity services for analysis and monitoring.
Money	Partners gain financial capitals from the provision of their offered services.
Services	Partners may provide specialised services or expertise to optimize data collection, integration, analysis, or other value-added services, such as legal and governmental clarifications and guidelines.

Operators: Operators play a crucial role in facilitating and managing the value creation processes within the Internet service provision space. They provide the technological infrastructure, platforms, tools, and services to enable secure and efficient digital connectivity sharing among stakeholders (Table 5).

Table 5 Operator(s)' Relation to Value Streams

Operator(s)' Relation to Value Streams	
Internet	Operator(s) manage the infrastructure sharing network, ensuring high-speed, security, privacy, and access control.
Money	Operator(s) will charge fees for network usage provided to stakeholders.
Services	Operator(s) offer services and capacity to ISPs to enhance the value derived from Internet connectivity.

Suppliers: Suppliers encompass entities or organizations that contribute to the Internet services provided within (Table 6).

Table 6 Suppliers' Relation to Value Streams

Suppliers' Relation to Value Streams	
Internet	Suppliers provide connectivity resources that form the foundation of the Internet network.
Money	Suppliers will receive financial compensation for their services.

Services	Suppliers may offer specialised services, technology solutions, or expertise to support Internet sharing, integration, or analysis.
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With the actors and value streams having been analysed, the actors of the value creation network of connectivity for the last-mile high-speed Internet in rural areas, considering the set of stakeholders presented above is as follows (Table 7):

Table 7 Clustering of the Stakeholders Categories into the Actors of Value Creation Network

Actors of Value Creation Network	Stakeholders Categorization
Customer	Farmers and Agricultural Producers
	Tourism, Environment and e-health stakeholders
	Business and Industry Stakeholders
	Government and Regulatory Bodies
	Research and Academic Institutions
Partners	Technology and Data Providers
	System Integrators
	Government and Regulatory Bodies
	Financial and Insurance Services
Suppliers	Internet Service Providers
	Technology and Data Providers
Operator(s)	Mobile Network Operators

After having clustered the set of stakeholders into the categories of the actors of the value creation network, according to their relation and interdependence with the value streams, the logical sequence is the provision of the respective value streams. For the value chain network for the last-mile high-speed Internet Connectivity initiative, the value stream is identified as follows (Figure 22):

Figure 22 Last-mile internet connectivity value stream

3.4 Business Models and XGain’s Use Cases

XGain’s overall project objective is to deliver a Knowledge Facilitation Tool (KFT), facilitating business model development, supporting decision-making in the selection of an ecosystem of technologies, consisting of connectivity options and edge processing solutions. Three types of actors could utilise the KFT, i) End Users (e.g. SMEs), ii) Internet Service Providers (ISPs) and iii) Public Authorities (e.g. National/Regional/local communities).

The development of the business models for XGain’s use cases entails identifying the problem(s) and needs that the innovative solutions are addressing, the target customers and users of the solutions, the value proposition differentiating and specifying the solutions based on sector and service provision, the channels through which the value proposition will be delivered, as well as the resources, activities and partnerships that are required for the successful exploitation and commercialization of the proposed solutions. The Business Model Canvas is a tool that can help in conducting these activities. Business Model Canvas is a strategic management tool widely used for developing new business models or documenting existing ones. It is indeed a great tool to represent linear aspects of businesses, however it may have drawbacks in capturing models where different players are involved and there are different customer journeys, depending on their needs, motivation to join, involvement in the value creation process, etc. (Osterwalder et al, 2011).

One of these “different players” as stated above are Public Authorities, whether at National, Regional or local community levels. Rather than viewing the overall process of value capture, creation, and delivery carried out by the business’ various elements and stakeholders, towards successful and profitable business as in the case of a Business Model Canvas, Public Authorities are aiming to improve governance and value creation towards society. Therefore, a differentiated Business Model Canvas will be used- The Public Governance Model (Martins et al, 2019). This model has similar initiatives in the form of results-oriented management models, involving emerging issues such as quality and organizational capacities (Barnard, 1971; Burns, 1978; Mintzberg, 1973; Prahalad and Hamel, 1990), networks and network governance (Agranoff, 2007; Castells, 2013), improved performance (Bouckaert & Halligan, 2008; Boyne, Meier, O’toole et al., 2006; Halachmi & Bouckaert, 1996; Neely, 2007), and public value creation (Moore, 1994, 1995).

Based upon the technological enablers (Drones, Satellite, Balloon etc.) as well as the sector (Aquaculture, Agriculture, etc.) and the specified services provided in each use case (e.g. Precision Agriculture, e-Health, etc.), XGain’s initial business models are designed and presented below, using the Business Model Canvas (for End users and ISPs) by identifying the nine-building blocks involved. For Public authorities, a modified (governance) Business Model Canvas will be presented. **Our aim is to fine tune them accordingly in real-time and real circumstances during the implementation and execution of the use cases (M16-M35).**

The following Business Model Canvases have been designed based on two fundamental assumptions stemming from XGain’s use case scenarios.

A) All XGain’s use cases have been designed and will be implemented as “enhancers” or “data rate multipliers” or as an addition of existing mobile networks in rural areas (characterised by low-speed or coverage fragmentation), providing high data rates and thus, harmonise to the latest digital technology tools and needs that require high-speed internet connections (e.g. video transfer in real time), area coverage as well as adequate network capacity.

B) XGain’s Business Model Canvases will be designed based on “Last-Mile” Internet Service Provision (ISP) (i.e. the service provider sells Internet services to the end users over a network provider’s connectivity network) and its added value. The “last-mile” is the part of a telecommunications network that delivers connectivity directly to a user’s device or to a local terminal in a home, business, or community location that provides last-inch service using Wi-Fi.

XGain acknowledges that the involved actors (as named above) have different Business and Societal interests (e.g. Public Authorities). As such we are presenting below initial Business Models, for each use case, as a basis for further elaboration and fine-tuning in real-time circumstances. BMs have been designed driven by three different questions (one for each actor).

- **End Users** – What is the added value for my business if I acquire high-speed internet connection?
- **Internet Service Providers**- Why should I invest and sell digital connectivity?
- **Public Authorities** – What is the societal/economic impact if we invest in digital connectivity?

In this section and at this time point of the project duration (M13) we are presenting initial BMs for End Users, ISPs and Public Authorities. XGain acknowledges the business-wise diversity of end users and ISPs as well as the variety of National, Regional and local rural community societal needs and ambitions. As such, all BMs will

be adjusted during the life-span of each use case (Starting at M16) through the interaction of use case leaders, related stakeholders and public authorities, in a real-time and real-circumstances environment and they will be presented in their full perspectives in the 2nd iteration of XGain's Business Model deliverable at M27.

3.4.1 Use Case #1 Rural Community Services

USE CASE 1	Catalonia, Spain
Leader	I2CAT
Sector	Agriculture, Environmental Monitoring, Education, Tourism
Services	a) Drones operation in rural areas, b) Additional services with high data rate

Location Needs: With the introduction of 5G communications and smart drones to the agricultural sector, a whole new array of methods opens up to address everyday needs and concerns. The capabilities and the usage of smart drones are vast, yet understanding how to operate them, as well developing and validating the services for said drones requires a dedicated space, which is to be deployed in this use case.

Motivation: The access to state-of-the-art technologies for radio access, like 5G, is sparse or even non-existent in rural areas. Equipped with sensors or even actuators, unmanned, remote-controlled devices (drones) introduce a great variety of functionalities and potential benefits for the productivity, quality and return value of rural services.

The use of drones and similar technologies requires powerful and fast connectivity to unlock their full potential. Real-time high-definition transmission of video is just one possible scenario in which 5G is necessary to satisfy the technical requirements and this is why the presence of such radio technology is very important for rural areas. Another reason for justifying the use of 5G to enable drone use cases in rural/remote areas is the fact that in towns and cities there are strict regulations for the operation of drones, which make it difficult to train the use of these devices.

Legacy communications (e.g., Wi-Fi) cannot meet the stringent performance requirements of automated drone operations that require real time (and mission critical) communications. It is therefore necessary to facilitate high throughput (e.g., for transmitting high resolution video streams or other sensor data), low latency (i.e., control channel, mission coordination) and reliable communications that can be achieved through 5G technology.

Solution: The Spanish pilot aims to deliver a space in a rural area that can be used to work and play with drones without any restrictions and having all the necessary radio and edge technologies to implement any type of services they might implement. In the context of rural environments, real-time crop monitoring across wide areas, ad-hoc pest-detection or automated area surveillance are just some of the tasks that can be performed by drones. The region in which the pilot will be executed features agriculture using many plantations (fruits, vegetables), but also other types of services. This includes tourism and logistics.

Impact to the community: The testbed in Mora la Nova aims to bring 5G technologies to rural areas, far away from big cities, to nurture and foster its use among local education institutions, the agricultural sector, and SMEs in general. Furthermore, working on the design of an economically and ecologically sustainable model for rural

5G- based networks is on the roadmap for this testbed, seeking tight collaboration with national and possible local network operators to maximise the relevance for the testbed, its users and the local community.

Business Model Canvas for End Users: Local agriculture and SMEs that plan to extend their service offerings with the usage of smart drones, but also other potential users of the drone operations centre, to either get in touch with the technologies or to test their solutions in a sandbox environment. Later use of the drone centre could be monetised, with customers paying for testbed access and support for testing/evaluating their services/solutions

Business Model Canvas for End Users

Figure 23 Business Model Canvas for End Users- UC1

Business Model Canvas for Internet Service Providers

Figure 24 Business Model Canvas for ISPs- UC1

The Public Governance Model Canvas for Public Authorities

Figure 25 The Public Governance Model Canvas for Public Authorities- UC1

3.4.2 Use Case #2 Rural Services, e-Health

USE CASE 2	Greece
Leader	CAP
Sector	e-Health, e-Governance, Education, Tourism
Services	a) eHealth robots for elderly, b) High data rate services, and c) Tourism

Location Needs: Central Macedonia makes up 26% of the country's primary sector whereas it is in the top 5 areas of tourism in Greece. Apart from the urban area of Thessaloniki, the region consists of multiple smaller cities and a diverse rural community covering mountain and coastal areas.

Motivation: The capacity and skills in the Central Macedonia region along with the long-term vision for the EU's rural areas, proposing a rural pact and action plan aimed at making those regions connected, and prosperous, is in line with the need of 5G and connectivity technologies.

The location in which the use case will be presented is in the Region of Central Macedonia, on the outskirts of the town of Thessaloniki. It is called Vasilika and it is located in a plain, the valley of the Anthemounda river. Providing adequate services to the whole population of the region is of foremost importance. A special interest is given to the elderly, the possibility to provide high data rate services (e.g., distance learning) and the possibility to valorise the touristic facilities needed for the summer months as an asset to the local community.

Solution: The pilot focuses on the importance of social interaction and caregiving of elderly people, showcasing how beneficial state of the art technologies can be. An e-Health Robot is going to act as a virtual caregiver to monitor and give advice to older adults. It comes with some interventions that enhance well-being which is focused on cognitive exercise, nutritional guidance, physical exercise and social recommendations.

Virtual attendance to various events is facilitated to boost elderly's wellness through cognitive games and quizzes. E-Health robot is going to suggest online workshops that are closed to older adults' interests. Optionally, people could participate in social interactions with other users.

At the same time there is a potential to enhance connectivity and processing capabilities in farming, to address the demand in the area. The primary sector of development (agriculture, greenhouse crops, animal husbandry) in the municipal unit of Vasilika, constitutes the main employment in the area in which the pilot will be executed.

Impact to the community: The region of Central Macedonia aims to develop a strong digital technology industry and rural development, as it is the major domain of activities in the region now. However, usually people in the rural areas have lower levels of e-literacy and digital skills. In addition, tourism plays an important role to the local economy. Hence, managing to address digital needs in both sectors and parallel increasing the services for the local population would have a direct positive impact to the lives of the local population.

Business Model Canvas for End Users: Currently, the region’s SME’s in the rural areas of Central Macedonia lack the opportunity to establish networks within and beyond the region. This limits the enterprises’ ability to build collaborations with R&D institutions, to modernize their production and develop export capacities. The current RIS3 Strategy of Central Macedonia marginally recognizes the importance of rural areas and their potential for the economic competitiveness of the region. Regional SMEs can significantly benefit from targeted digital services providing 5G connectivity and technological advancements for supporting such networks and architectures. For the purpose of this Use Case, as end users will include SMEs such as elderly houses as well as those implicated in the tourism and farming sectors.

Figure 26 Business Model Canvas for End Users- UC2

Business Model Canvas for Internet Service Providers

Figure 27 Business Model Canvas for ISPs- UC2

The Public Governance Model Canvas for Public Authorities

Figure 28 The Public Governance Model Canvas for Public Authorities- UC2

3.4.3 Use Case #3 Remote Community

USE CASE 3	UK
Leader	CAFA
Sector	Agriculture, Tourism, Environmental Monitoring
Services	a) Precision Agriculture and b) Tourism

Location Needs: In remote islands, like Scilly, there exist several blind spots (i.e., not connected areas) due to fragmented network coverage. Although there were some initiatives in the past to establish 4G services, and currently 5G, there is still not complete network coverage for the island. To benefit from the full potential of digitalization and services provided through connectivity there is a need to ensure network availability in near-all areas of the island (*5G is already deployed in some areas, but there are several “dead points”, i.e., blind spots*).

Motivation: A small-scale vegetable farm on the Isles of Scilly, will act as a demonstration farm showcasing connectivity solutions addressing the application requirements and needs of the farm. Particularly, to showcase the advantage of having a digital farm, precision agriculture techniques will be adopted. More precisely, soil, water and meteorological sensors may be deployed, creating in real time the digital footprint of the farm and its related operation. In addition, the owner is a provider of summer houses for tourists, a new sector for the local economy with great potential aiming to identify common opportunities for network coverage for the farm and touristic experiences during the summer months.

Solution: A series of sensors will be deployed in the farm, forming the input data sources for a digital twin that can be used for the optimisation of production such as optimised water management, and monitoring of the production quality. For the scenario demonstration soil, water, meteorological sensors, and cameras to monitor the field will be used. All sensors will be connected to an edge device where pre-processing of the collected data will take place. The connectivity between the edge and the core network will be expanded by the usage of aerial radio relay aerostats ensuring the connectivity till the next connected area of the island. Apart from the Scilly farm, the expansion of the tested and validated solutions will be investigated for the whole island. This can be achieved by means of aerostats/drones that will provide adequate and extended network coverage. Research conducted on the Scilly farm site, being the initial testbed, will provide the means to calculate the volume of aerostats/drones needed to cover the whole island, aiming at 100% coverage of the area, ensuring that no one is left behind, sharing the lessons learned, and providing access of services to the growing parts to the overall community.

Impact to the community: Apart from the precision agriculture scenario that will be demonstrated, offering 5G coverage to the whole island has a wider impact to the local community. Ensuring that 100% of the island stakeholders can learn from (but not limited to) the local businesses in other sectors (e.g., outdoor recreation, clean energy), will realise the XGain initiative to offer improved services for agriculture, ground maintenance, recycling companies and other domains to the local and currently disconnected communities.

Business Model Canvas for End Users: There is a clear need in the local community to collaborate to cover parts of the island with no connectivity especially considering the needs that arise during the summer months with the rise of Tourism at the island.

Figure 29 Business Model Canvas for End Users- UC3

Business Model Canvas for Internet Service Providers

Figure 30 Business Model Canvas for ISPs- UC3

The Public Governance Model Canvas for Public Authorities

Figure 31 The Public Governance Model Canvas for Public Authorities- UC3

3.4.4 Use Case #4 Farming and Forestry

USE CASE 4	LITHUANIA
Leader	ART
Sector	Farming and Forestry
Services	a) Precision Agriculture, b) Forest Management

Location Needs: As the deployment of 5G network in Lithuania already started, and currently there are about 40 base stations operating, the selected location (i.e., farm) will not be far away from populated and connected areas, where 5G network is expanding. To collect the data, a crop farm has been selected, as the current hyperspectral data processing system is tailored to work with such crops as wheat, barley and rapeseed.

Motivation: Innovative crop assessment technology based on drones/planes and hyperspectral cameras are already designed and used. Developed solutions empowers better understanding of crop health, nutrient composition and even more accurate disease or stress detection. However, as it is based on multidimensional data aggregation and heavy load computation, current situation in rural connectivity limits its usage to the bigger/corporate farms. For smaller farm sites, uncontrolled data transmissions (i.e., send all that you sense) may result in significant delays when sensed data (facilitated e.g., through drone monitoring) originate from disconnected areas, and also induce additional costs when transmitting voluminous data streams (e.g., video) to a remote server, for instance, over a cellular channel. It is therefore of paramount importance to provide hybrid solutions of local (e.g., on drone or local server processing) as well as edge or cloud-based solutions, to efficiently handle data transferring from areas with limited internet connectivity such as a farm field of forests.

Solution: The main aim of this Use Case is to provide Forest monitoring and evaluation of certain properties (e.g. fire risk, pest infestation, drought affected areas, etc.). The developed service will be based on a multirotor drone equipped with high-end hyperspectral camera-able to provide valuable information via the collection of a vast amount of data therefore a lot of processing power is required to extract and infer the results from the raw data. Our approach will eliminate the time needed to transfer and analyse data resulting in faster human decisions and responses. This precious time can be saved by using new connectivity technologies such as 5G. The envisioned service will be using 5G network to transmit raw or pre-processed data, thus providing results of the hyperspectral analysis to the end user much faster.

Impact to the community: The envisioned services will have a direct impact on precision agriculture and/or environmental (forest, land, water, air) monitoring and control. The stakeholders could be not only larger farms, but also state institutions, and environmental agencies, strengthening the sustainability of biodiversity and other socio-economic aspects. The envisioned precision farming system will allow the determination of water content in plants, macro (nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium) and micro (iron, manganese, zinc, copper) nutritional elements, the lack of chemical and nutritional elements at different stages of plant growth. Knowing an exact situation in the field can help farmers to easily detect problems and exact locations, plant fertilisation, spraying and other activities based on actual plant needs, divide the field into parametric zones for variable rate application and generate maps for autonomous machinery.

Business Model Canvas for End Users

Figure 32 Business Model Canvas for End Users- UC4

Business Model Canvas for Internet Service Providers: The solution can be distributed: i) as a service, where a farmer can purchase a service to scan his fields. In such a case the farmer would be charged based on the area that needs to be mapped. ii) as an infrastructure as a service (IaaS) model, when the farmer uses his own drone equipped with hyperspectral cameras, or buys field scanning service from a third party located closer to the farm. In this case, a farmer is charged based on the data amount to be processed as well as a subscription fee for the access to the information system providing the tools for analysis and decision making.

Figure 33 Business Model Canvas for ISPs- UC4

The Public Governance Model Canvas for Public Authorities

Figure 34 The Public Governance Model Canvas for Public Authorities- UC4

3.4.5 Use Case #5 Aquaculture

USE CASE 5	CROATIA
Leader	BENCO
Sector	Aquaculture, Environmental Monitoring
Services	a) Water Quality Monitoring, b) Remote Oyster Farming

Location Needs: Remote coastal or open sea areas are usually underdeveloped in terms of ICT infrastructure, hindering wider digitalization efforts due to lack of connectivity. This is especially true for aquaculture, which remains one of the least digitized sectors of the food value chain. The long coastal areas of the Dalmatia region in Croatia have fragmented 3G/4G/5G coverage which significantly limits transmission opportunities and thus the digitalization of services in certain areas.

Motivation: For the oyster farming industry to survive the global warming crisis, it is crucial to apply innovative changes during the whole process of operation. The new situation requires further adjustments, and, in this case, it is the digitization and automation of the oyster farming sector. The main obstacle that delays this transition is limited connectivity. Most farms are located in coastal rural areas where the population size may not be commercially attractive for an MNO. Even if the broad area is serviced by an MNO, quite often farms are located far from the coast and thus reside outside radio coverage. For the oyster farm in Dalmatia, human-assisted data collection establishes the digital footprint of the farm, i.e., manual data collection from sensors by field personnel. However, such data collection schemes are inefficient and result in additional costs and extra delays, as they require frequent travels from shore to farm, and vice versa. It is therefore crucial to establish networking solutions for automated data gathering by using remotely (offshore) located water quality (and other) sensors, providing to the oyster farm monitoring system the necessary data for operations optimization and cost reduction. The main problem is how to ensure fast and reliable data transfer from the receiver (offshore) to the end user (nearshore and/or onshore) when connectivity options are limited.

Solution: This Use Case will demonstrate how an extended network infrastructure developed using LoRaWAN and satellite communication can transmit data from offshore sensors to the central monitoring system thus, enhance the digitization and automation of the oyster farming sector.

Particularly the sensors will be connected to the receiver (stations floating on water, float/buoy aid) via underwater cables. Multiple nearby stations will be connected to a LoRaWAN network, where an edge device aggregates data, pre-process it, and transmits (either raw or processed) data to other existing platforms and monitoring services. The satellite IoT network of XGain's partner- ASTRO will be employed to retrieve data from the edge device.

The service is a periodic data transmission of the water quality parameters in the environment where oysters are farmed. The availability of satellite data transmission will determine the data collection and transmission period. Farmers will be able to remotely monitor the water quality parameters and plan their farming procedures accordingly.

Impact to the Farm/Community: The Dalmatian Hinterland ranges in width from fifty kilometres in the north to just a few kilometres in the south. Usually, family-owned oyster farms dominate in Croatia and produce 50

tons of oysters per year, while several large farms grew up in the last decade (e.g., of magnitude up to 8 regular family oyster farms). The use of intelligent monitoring system technologies would provide sustainable business models for local farms by increasing the yield of cultivated products and the efficiency of farm operations, as well as opening global market opportunities.

Business Model Canvas for End Users

Figure 35 Business Model Canvas for End Users- UC5

Business Model Canvas for Internet Service Providers: The solution could be distributed using two models: hardware as a service (HaaS) and Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS). In the case of HaaS, a client could rent a complete set of hardware, including deployment of the network. The client would be billed monthly, based on the amount of sensor systems deployed. In the case of IaaS, the client should use his own hardware or purchase devices. This model charges the client based on the amount of data to be transmitted.

Figure 36 Business Model Canvas for ISPs- UC5

The Public Governance Model Canvas for Public Authorities

Figure 37 The Public Governance Model Canvas for Public Authorities- UC5

3.4.6 Use Case #6 Livestock and Farming

USE CASE 6	BELGIUM
Leader	EVILVO
Sector	Livestock and Farming
Services	a) Livestock Health, b) Farm Management

Location Needs: Flanders is in general a densely populated area, with communication infrastructure in place. However, even within Flanders, there are differences in connectivity between different areas, providers and devices. Traditionally, Flanders is very active in the farming industry but the available arable lands and pastures of each farmer are spread across multiple smaller fields in the same, or neighbouring villages.

Motivation: Already, a digital divide can be observed between extensive and intensive livestock farming. The XGain scope aims to address this void by developing a ‘digital shepherd’, in two forms: (a) a camera system in the field that monitors the herd in pastures of relatively small size; (b) a drone that independently and regularly checks the herd in remote areas. These relatively small pastures are typically found in Belgium but also in other EU regions, densely populated, which are typically well-connected areas. On the other hand, large pastures or nature reserves can be found in remote areas (e.g., mountains) where network support is limited or non-existing.

Solution: Through installation of camera’s and other IoT sensors such as flow sensor and RFID antenna on the drinking bin the farmer will be able to observe his animals remotely. A digital shepherd will support the farmers’ daily operation (e.g., livestock monitoring) will be developed, considering areas with both strong and poor network coverage. Real-time monitoring services will thus ensure that animals (cows/sheep) are always observed, capturing relevant events for the farmer with a risk of health and welfare issues, and additionally generating targeted alerts. The digital shepherd will have a direct impact on productivity and welfare of the livestock, but also reduce stress for the farmer. In addition, smart algorithms could analyse the data to provide the farmer with key statistics throughout the whole grazing period.

Impact to the community: Outdoor livestock monitoring is extremely valuable for the health and welfare of the animals and is of paramount importance for the individual farmer but also for the livestock industry. In many regions of Europe, cows/sheep/goats are grazing at vast outdoor areas for extended periods (e.g., for a significant part of the year). In Flanders, beef cattle and small ruminants are often kept in relative confined/controlled areas. Dairy cows have been more intensively monitored to be able to maintain high productivity and health under controlled circumstances, but the reverse movement is also going on under pressure of consumers with concerns about animal welfare. However, it is key to keep the same level of monitoring and care maintained outdoors compared to indoors, and that is where this technology can make the difference.

Business Model Canvas for End Users

Figure 38 Business Model Canvas for End Users- UC6

Business Model Canvas for Internet Service Providers: Potential business models could be hardware purchase costs combined with Software as a Service (SaaS). Alternatively, the hardware itself could also be provided as a service (HaaS) with all costs included in a monthly/yearly fee.

Figure 39 Business Model Canvas for ISPs- UC6

The Public Governance Model Canvas for Public Authorities

Figure 40 The Public Governance Model Canvas for Public Authorities- UC6

4 Knowledge Facilitation Tool (KFT)

As stated above, XGain’s overall project objective is to deliver a Knowledge Facilitation Tool (KFT), facilitating business model development, **supporting decision-making** in the selection of an ecosystem of technologies, consisting of connectivity options and edge processing solutions (Figure 41). Furthermore, XGain will coherently proceed in assessing their socio-economic and techno-environmental effects, aiming at: **increasing systemic resilience** and **energy efficiency**; contributing to **climate mitigation**; and reducing the **digital divides** between different types of farms, sectors and regions. In this respect, XGain fosters a sustainable, balanced, and inclusive development of rural, coastal and urban areas by facilitating access to relevant stakeholders, such as end Users and their associations, Public Authorities, policymakers and ISPs, to a comprehensive inventory of smart XG, last-mile connectivity and edge computing solutions, and of related assessment methods.

Figure 41 The KFT interface

4.1 The KFT environment, user selection (Input), Business Models and Explanatory narratives (output)

The objective is to design and implement a user-friendly web-based tool to allow the intuitive usage of the XGain Knowledge Facilitation Tool from mainly, non-expert personnel. To ensure the multi-actor engagement and make the output of the Knowledge Facilitation Tool feasible for non-scientists, a user-friendly Human Machine Interface (HMI) will be designed after capturing the requirements and technical specifications from the users (input) to develop the detailed low-level design of the HMI. The user shall be able to select a specific

sector and service or multisectoral assessments, dedicated services (Figure 42), provide as input location needs and machinery needs and actuators (Figure 43), service demand volumes and specificities (Figure 44) and identify the level of the performed assessment (Regional, Community, Farm Level). Based on the user input and the outcome of the pre-processing, a light-weight recommender system will propose to the user(s) an indicative list of the stock of connectivity and edge processing solutions. The intelligence of the recommender will rely on a matchmaking engine that will bridge the user needs with the presumed technologies. This adaptive phase will be implemented through a promoting/demoting method by using the results of the environmental/social/financial assessment (see chapter 4.2) of the ecosystem of technologies and the feedback of the users through an accept/decline model (Figure 45).

An in-depth analysis of the KFT regarding the overall environment as well as its architecture design and technical specifications can be found on XGain’s project deliverables D4.7-version1 (M16) and D2.7- version 1 (M9).

Figure 42 KFT’s sector and service selection

Figure 43 KFT's Location details selection

Figure 44 KFT's Service requirements selection

Figure 45 KFT’s summary results selection outputs

Following user’s selection requirements in terms of sectors, services, actuators etc (as described above), the KFT will provide respective Business Models Canvases (output) assisted with complementary narratives explaining in non-technical/non-scientific terms the basic elements of the recommended Business Model Canvas.

An example of a BMC narrative can be the following, stemming from an indicative BMC for End users in the Lithuanian use case where drones will be used as high-speed connectivity enablers for precision agriculture and forest management. For this example, the choices will be:

Sector: Agriculture

Service: Precision agriculture

Terrain Type: Plain

Meteo: Humid

ICT Infrastructure: Wi-Fi

Machinery Actuators: Drone

“Utilisation of drones for high-speed internet connectivity will facilitate the transfer of high-volume hyperspectral camera data and provide valuable information, in real-time, for Precision Agriculture. A better and quicker understanding of crop health, nutrient composition and accurate disease or stress detection can reduce the excessive/unnecessary use of fertilisers and other chemicals towards lower production costs,

increase in healthier products and less environmental impact. Collectively, high-speed internet connectivity can increase profitability via reduced costs, increased crop production and internet sales (B2B, B2C)."

4.2 Socio-environmental and Techno-economic aspects (Outputs)

In addition to KFT's BMCs offered as pdfs (output) based on actor type, selection and requirements, XGain through its platform will incorporate quantifiable and semi-quantitative information into KFT's supporting decision-making processes by assessing i) the socio-economic and environmental implications of employing advanced last-mile connectivity and edge technology solutions in various sectors across Europe and ii) the techno-economic aspects for the deployment of the required Information and Communication Technology (ICT) investments including connectivity, edge processing, hardware and software solutions. This is of paramount importance for creating balanced, sustainable, and responsible outcomes.

XGain will carry out Cost Benefit Analyses (CBAs) at all three levels (i.e., farm, community and regional levels), to be built on previous examples of CBAs applied for technology developments in rural areas, resource use efficiency effects of agricultural sustainable intensification programs on agronomic, environmental, economic, social, transgenerational and global dimensions as well as conservation and livelihood. XGain will further extend the CBAs to conduct socio-economic, climate and environmental Multicriteria analysis (MCA) impact assessments of the selected co-created digital solutions identified to; compare them, link them with the level of urgencies at farm-level, community level and regional level and to recommend most feasible innovative and smarter solutions that gain high acceptability locally and can increase access to services, opportunities, and adequate innovation ecosystems at a larger scale.

All impact assessments will assess digital solutions against a status quo; to compare a social, environmental, and economic situation with and without high tech future oriented (foresight) solutions. CBAs will be conducted on the ground of existing datasets and data selected in each use case, so as to find impacts of high-tech interventions, assessing a series of quantitative ecosystem service indicators, following a production, regulation and cultural ecosystem service approach. These assessments indicators include:

- **Economic indicators** at farm level such as gross revenue (€), gross margin (€), labour use at farm/ in value-chain (hours), annual work units (AWUs) and seasonality (hours/month) among others.
- **Environmental and climate indicators** at farm and community levels, including environmental agriculture cover (%), environmental number of reared animals (number), environmental animal richness (number), environmental plant richness (number), environmental water bodies (ha), environmental burned area (ha), environmental forest area (ha), environmental erosion control index (unitless), environmental protected areas (%), environmental Sites of Community Importance (SCI) area.
- **Climate indicators** particularly relevant at community and regional levels, including crop diversity (number of crops cultivated), soil coverage (%), water use (m³), nitrogen use (kg), electrical power (MWh), thermal power (MWh) and CO₂ emissions (tons).
- **Socio-economic indicators** at community and regional levels, including; ageing index (%), social cumulative population growth rate (%), social medium-high education ratio (%), ratio of the population with medium or higher education to the overall population (%), social schools/libraries per inhabitant, social health centres per inhabitant (%), social workers in the commerce sector (%), social vacancies in nursing homes (%), economic employment rate (%), economic activity rate (%), economic area of retail activities (m²), economic working licences on the services sector (%).

It should be stressed that the techno-economic and socio-environmental methodology/framework is a significant part of the Knowledge Facilitation Tool (KFT). The techno-economic methodology allows the estimation of deployment and operation cost of connectivity, edge solutions and/or enablers in case of individual users as well as the extra functionality to calculate potential revenues in case of communities, regions or network providers. The socio-economic and environmental methodology/framework will provide a blueprint for evaluating how these technologies can enhance efficiency, reduce costs, and support improved decision-making processes for various stakeholders while carefully considering the associated socio-economic and environmental impacts.

XGain will proceed to the incorporation of the above quantifiable and semi-quantitative analyses into the KFT tool. These analyses will “enrich” the recommender system and act as “weights” of KFT’s supporting decision-making as they will directly correlate with the business model outputs. As such, the user will be able to select the spectrum of impacts associated with the adoption and integration of edge technologies based on their interests and needs (Figure 46).

Figure 46 Tecno-economic and Socio-economic and environmental impact assessment selection.

Incorporating socio-environmental and techno-economic considerations into decision making is a dynamic process that requires ongoing commitment and adaptability. XGain embraces these principles aiming towards

well-informed decisions that balance economic, social, and environmental concerns for the benefit of all stakeholders.

Further in depth elaboration on the techno-economic and socio-economic and environmental aspects of XGain’s use cases can be found in the deliverables D4.1 “Techno-economic assessment of last-mile and edge technological solutions (1st version)” delivered at M12 and D4.3 “Socio-environmental Assessment of Last-mile and Edge Technological Solutions (Version 1)” delivered at M12, stemming from XGain’s tasks T4.1 “Techno-economic Assessment of Last-mile and Edge technological solutions” and task T4.2 “T4.2 Socio- environmental Assessment of Last-mile and Edge Technological Solutions” respectively.

4.3 Value-Analytic Hierarchy Process (V-AHP). Methodology and attributes

Collectively, for the creation of KFT’s business model output(s), the **Value-Analytic Hierarchy Process (V-AHP)** was followed.

The Value-Analytic Hierarchy Process (V-AHP) is a decision-making methodology that extends the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) to include value-based considerations in the decision-making process. AHP is a structured technique for dealing with complex decisions by breaking them down into a hierarchical structure and assessing the relative importance of criteria and alternatives. Value-AHP builds upon this framework by incorporating the concept of value, which is often essential in real-world decision-making scenarios. XGain’s simplified version of the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) – is presented in Figure 47.

Based on the V-AHP and taking into consideration the complexity of last-mile internet connectivity and its added value offered to KFT’s users towards the support in their decision-making, XGain’s methodology follows the indicative steps presented below:

- A) **Define the decision problem:** To create the best business model solution for last-mile digital connectivity
- B) **Identify criteria and alternatives:** To utilise and incorporate techno-economic and socio-economic and environmental aspects in the decision-making
- C) **Assign weights to the criteria:** To proceed with criteria pairwise comparisons based on their “weights” of their importance
- D) **Assess alternative performance:** To evaluate how well each alternative performs with respect to each criterion
- E) **Calculate the Value Scores:** To calculate the value scores for each alternative by multiplying the performance scores by the respective criteria weights and aggregating them
- F) **Select the best alternative:** To provide a business model with the highest value score as the best choice based on the decision criteria and their associated values

At the present time frame of the project (M13), XGain’s consortium has proceeded with the following steps and actions based on the V-AHP methodology as presented in Figure 47:

- Benchmarking and selection of the business model canvas as a BM framework (Figure 47, step 1) as described in chapters 2.3 and 2.4
- Identification of BM framework criteria (Figure 47, step 2) based on a number of parameters such as clarity and simplicity, plasticity, value capture, collaboration etc, as described in chapter 2.3.1, and

- Initial identification of quantitative and/or qualitative criteria (Figure 47, step 5) stemming from the techno-economic and socio-economic and environmental analyses, described in chapter 4.2

Figure 47 XGain's Business Model decision support system process

For the remaining steps of XGain's Business Model decision support system process as presented in Figure 47, XGain will undertake the following actions:

- Rating AHP of the proposed BM framework criteria as well as identification of alternatives (steps 3 and 4) will be validated in the actual XGain's use cases (M16) where relevant stakeholders and decision-makers in the AHP process will ensure that the criteria reflect their perspectives and preferences and possibly propose or add alternative ways for business models.
- Rating of quantitative and qualitative criteria, assignment of "weights", pairwise comparisons and value calculations towards the incorporation and construction of BM alternatives and final best BM selection (KFT output) as presented in Figure 47 (steps 6-9) will also be applied and validated in the actual XGain's use cases (M16).

XGain recognises the importance and complexity of V-AHP implementation. Careful consideration of how to quantify and incorporate value into the decision process has been thought, designed and implemented in XGain, through 3 dedicated tasks (T4.1-T4.3), undertaken by experienced consortium partners. XGain will ensure that the accuracy of the data during the implementation of the use cases and the judgments made during the pairwise comparisons will be used with caution and with a clear understanding of the decision context.

5 Next steps

5.1 Testing and validation

Building upon the Knowledge Facilitation Tool (T4.4) and the techno-economic and socio-environmental assessments (T4.2, T4.3), XGain’s innovative business models will be adjusted and fine-tuned in 6 real life use cases, starting in M16 in 6 different European countries. Under real-circumstances and in real-time, relevant stakeholders such as use case organisers, local public authorities, MNOs and others, will provide valuable information in finalising additions, specificities, exceptions, misjudgements and possible failures in XGain’s preliminary innovative business models.

Following testing and validation in XGain’s use cases the business models will enrich the recommender system (and enriched by) and will be linked to a set of parameters (e.g., connectivity and edge processing solutions, specific location needs, rural services) to establish a dynamic selection process. Business model analysis will take into account aspects related to the mixture of services to be supported, the resulting sharing of (and added value gained from) the underlying infrastructure, and corresponding services, and also the novel infrastructure/resource capabilities coming with the 5G technology ecosystem, e.g., network slicing (sharing), to deliver documented suggestions on sustainable business models for the situation at hand, including vertical, collaborative and broker based schemes.

Further enrichment of the recommender system will be accomplished with the incorporation of the techno-economic and socio-economic and environmental aspects and their respective “weights” leading to innovative business models associated with last-mile internet connectivity in specific sectors in European rural areas, paving the way towards increased capacity of farmers, foresters and rural communities through connectivity gains.

Testing and validation are crucial processes in the development of the KFT digital platform to ensure that it meets its intended functionality, performance, security, and usability requirements.

6 Conclusions

This deliverable constitutes the first version of the “XGain Business Models” (D4.5, M13). In this deliverable, a thorough investigation and recommendation of the Business Model Framework was conducted leading to the Business Model Canvas as the appropriate tool. The Business Model Canvas is able to provide a quick overview of the last-mile internet connectivity and the added value that this technology can provide to users (End Users, ISPs) for specific sectors (e.g., Aquaculture, Agriculture, etc.) and specific services (e.g., Precision Agriculture, Precision Aquaculture etc.) based on XGain’s 6 use cases.

The Business Model Canvas template was filled in, and the analysis described the value sharing model among the actors; the targeted customers and their relationships; the appropriate channels; the main activities, resources and partners; the revenue streams; and the cost structure of the alliance. This analysis sets the basis for the future business plan(s) of XGain’s use cases, offered as a decision support tool by XGain’s KFT.

Contrary to the business-oriented needs and ambitions (profit) stemming from end users and ISPs, XGain also recognises the need for internet connectivity, in today’s digitalised world, as a public good (just like a road or a bridge). Therefore, a modified business model canvas (Governance canvas) was also used in an attempt to showcase and pinpoint to public authority users all the requirements, collaborations etc. that can facilitate valuable impact to society and businesses through high-speed internet connectivity.

Through desk research, the authors of this deliverable tried to investigate and benchmark existing business models (state of play), for all the questioned sectors, in terms of the added value that last-mile internet connectivity has offered. Furthermore, the same attempt was tried for identifying how last-mile connectivity has aided in the growth (or not) of the respective market sectors, especially in rural areas. Both of these attempts were unsuccessful due to the lack of information and available data in such specialised concepts.

Lack of information for business models addressing last-mile internet connectivity in specific rural area sectors identifies the need towards the absolute necessity in creating new, specialised ones, taking into consideration parameters such as techno-economic and socio-economic and environmental impacts that these technologies require and create respectively.

The second deliverable (D4.6) “XGain Business models”, due M27, will be an updated version of the current deliverable. It will provide improvements and enhancements on the content of Business Models based on their “fine tuning” in the actual use cases (starting M16) where validation and impact assessment will take place in real-time under real-life circumstances.

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